

Compléments à l'article *Literatur* de D.O.Edzard, RIA 7, 1/2 (1987) 35-48 (choix)¹

Pascal Attinger, 2021

Adapa: A. Cavigneaux, ZA 104 (2014) 1-41; A. Annus, SAAS 24 (2016) 14-16 et 105-110. — Cf. S.J. Milstein, ZA 105 (2015) 30-41; ead., Tracking the Master Scribe: Revision through Introduction in Biblical and Mesopotamian Literature (2016) 76-109 passim.

Angim dimma (3.1.a): Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 377-389; ETCSL 1.6.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, Mitologia sumerica (2001) 235-246; Black et alii, LAS 181-186; Attinger/A. Glenn, TTS (2017). — Cf. Bruschweiler, Inanna 73 sq.; Wilcke, Politik und Literatur 60 sq.; Penglase, Greek Myths 55-60; M. Streck, Or. 71 (2002) 225-227; Wagensooner, Götterreisen (2005) 129-132; I. Vorontsov, NABU 2008/24; J.-D. Forest,

¹¹ Non enregistrés ici sont les nouveaux duplicats et les comptes rendus des éditions. La date figurant après les renvois à ETCSL est celle de "editor: standardisation, proofreading, (adapting) translation", car les corrections postérieures sont de caractère mineur. J'ai fait une exception pour Gudam, qui mentionne des "major corrections". Les abréviations utilisées sont en général celles de P. Attinger, *Eléments de linguistique sumérienne*. [...] (Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis Sonderband, Fribourg Suisse/Göttingen, 1993); ajouter: Attinger, TTS = P. Attinger, Traductions de textes sumériens (<http://www.iaw.unibe.ch/atinger>); Black et alii, LAS = J. Black et alii, *The Literature of Ancient Sumer* (2004); Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* = J. Bottéro/S.N. Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme*. [...], Paris, 1989; Broekema, Inanna = H. Broekema, *Inanna, heerseres van hemel en aarde* [...] (2013); Clifford, *Creation Accounts* = R.J. Clifford, *Creation Accounts in the Ancient Near East and in the Bible* (= *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly Monograph Series* 26, 1994); DSSt: Datenbank der sumerischen Streitoliteratur (<http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/dsst/pager>); Delnero, *Variation* = P. Delnero, *Variation in Sumerian Literary Compositions: A Case Study Based on the Decad*. Ph. D., Univ. of Pennsylvania 2006; DSSt: Datenbank der sumerischen Streitoliteratur (<http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/dsst/pager>). Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* = A. Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic*, in: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *Women in the ancient Near East*, New York 2014, 28-58; Gadotti, *Sumerian wisdom literature* = A. Gadotti, *Sumerian wisdom literature*, in: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *Women in the ancient Near East*, New York 2014, 59-74; Hruška, *Ackerbau* = B. Hruška, *Tradiční obilnárství staré Mezopotámie [Der traditionelle Ackerbau im alten Mesopotamien]*, Prague, 1990; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once...* = Th. Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* [...], Yale, 1987; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* = S.N. Kramer/J. Maier, *Myths of Enki, The Crafty God*, New York/Oxford, 1989; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* = S.N. Kramer, *El Matrimonio Sagrado en la Antigua Sumer. Traducción y adaptación de Manuel Molina* (= *Colección: Estudios Orientales* 11, 1999); Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* = G. Leick, *Sex and Eroticism in Mesopotamian Literature*, London/New York, 1994; Lisman, *At the beginning* = J.J.W. Lisman, *At the beginning... Cosmogony, theogony and anthropogony in Sumerian texts of the third and second millennium BCE*. Ph. D. Diss., Universiteit Leiden 2013; Mél. Hallo = M.E. Cohen/D.C. Snell/D.B. Weisberg (ed.), *The Tablet and the Scroll. Near Eastern Studies in Honor of WILLIAM W. HALLO*, Bethesda, 1993; Mém. Black = H.D. Baker et al. (ed.), *Your Praise is Sweet: A Memorial Volume for Jeremy Black from Students, Colleagues and Friends*, London 2010; *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* = M.E. Vogelzang/H.L.J. Vanstiphout (ed.), *Mesopotamian Epic Literature. Oral or Aural?*, Lewiston, 1992; Penglase, *Greek Myths* = C. Penglase, *Greek Myths and Mesopotamia* [...], London/New York, 1994; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* = J. Peterson, *A Study of Sumerian Faunal Conception with a Focus on the Terms Pertaining to the Order Testudines*, Ph. D. Diss., Univ. of Pennsylvania 2007; Raphael Kutscher Memorial Volume = A.F. Rainey (ed.), *kinattūtu ša dārāti*: Raphael Kutscher Memorial Volume, Tel Aviv, 1993; Rollinger, *Frühformen* = R. Rollinger, *Frühformen historischen Denkens* [...] (dissertation non pub., Innsbruck, 1993); *The Context of Scripture I* = W.W. Hallo/K. Lawson Younger, Jr. (ed.), *The Context of Scripture Vol. I: Canonical Compositions from the Biblical World*, Leiden, Boston, Köln 1997; *The Context of Scripture II* = W.W. Hallo/K. Lawson Younger, Jr. (ed.), *The Context of Scripture Vol. II: Monumental Inscriptions from the Biblical World*, Leiden, Boston, Köln 2000; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* = H. Vanstiphout, *Eduba. Schrijven en lezen in Sumer* (2004); Wagensooner, *Götterreisen* = K. Wagensooner, "Wenn Götter reisen ...". *Götterreisen, -prozessionen und Besuchsfahrten in den sumerischen literarischen Texten* (Diplomarbeit zur Erlangung des Magistergrades der Philosophie aus der Studienrichtung Altsemitische Philologie und Orientalische Archäologie eingereicht an der Universität Wien, 2005). Wilcke, *Anfänge* = C. Wilcke, *Vom altorientalischen Blick zurück auf die Anfänge*, dans: E. Angehrn (ed.), *Anfang und Ursprung. Die Frage nach dem Ersten in Philosophie und Kulturwissenschaft* (Colloquium Rauricum 10, 2007) 3-59. Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* = C. Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur im älteren Babylonien*, dans K. Raaflaub (ed.), *Anfänge politischen Denkens in der Antike* (= *Schriften des Historischen Kollegs, Kolloquien* 24, München, 1993) pp. 29-75.

Mém. Bottéro 45 sq.; 47-53 passim; L. Feldt, *Mém. Black* 69-92; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 43 sq. et 95-97; K. Wagensonner, dans: J. Braarvig/M.J. Geller (ed.), *Multilingualism, Lingua Franca and Lingua Sacra* (Max Planck Research Library for the History and Development of Knowledge Studies 10, 2018) 256-261 et 282-284.

Dumuzis Tod (3.1.b): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 28-46; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 300-312; ETCSL 1.4.3 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 229-241; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 492-507; Black et alii, *LAS* 77-84; Attinger, *TTS* (2009, actualisé en 2015); Attinger/J. Matuszak, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 399-414 et 441. — Cf. W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/1* (1986) 27-30 (ll. 15-69); T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 43-52; A. da Silva, *BCSMS* 22 (1991) 31-35; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 142-150; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT* 307 (2003) 97-102; D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) passim, surtout 301-308 (index des lignes discutées pp. 479 sq.); C. Hoffmann, *Dumuzi's Dream: Dream Analysis in Ancient Mesopotamia*, *Dreaming* 14 (2004) 240-251 (DuDr.: 240-247); P. Mander, *Canti sumerici d'amore e morte* (*Testi del Vicino Oriente antico* 2/8, 2005) 165-174 (traduction partielle); B. Alster, *ZA* 96 (2006) 1-30 (v. à ce propos P. Attinger, *NABU* 2006/69); Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 311-315; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 43-45, 54; J. Pfitzner, *SEL* 34-36 (2017-2019) 19-28; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 114-117; C. Saporetti, *I sogni degli antichi. La Mesopotamia e i popoli vicini* (2019) 133-137.

Enki und Ninḫursanga (3.1.c): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 181-204; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 151-164; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 363-386; ETCSL 1.1.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 150-164; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 155-170; P. Attinger, dans P. Jovanovic, *Le Mensonge Universel* (Paris: Le jardin des Livres 2007) 55-72; Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015); R. Jiménez Zamudio, *Isimu* 16 (2013) 13-38; T. Rodin, *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess: An Interpretation of Her Myths* (2014) 46-48, 111 sq., 115-228, 329-337 (trad.); Attinger, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 5-20 et 417. — Cf. R.S. Falkowitz, *Entretiens sur l'antiquité classique* 30 (1984) 15-18; Vanstiphout, *CRRAI* 33 (1986, ed. 1987) 166 sq.; H. Limet, dans F. Jouan et B. Deforge (ed.), *Peuples et pays mythiques. Actes du V^e Colloque du Centre de Recherches mythologiques de l'Université de Paris X (Chantilly, 18-20 septembre 1986)* (1988) 11-19; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 22-30; H. Limet, *Mél. Sjöberg* 357-360 et 364; Vanstiphout, *NABU* 1990/57; B.F. Batto, dans: K.L. Younger et alii (ed.), *The Biblical Canon in Comparative Perspective. Scripture in Context IV* (1991) 33-66; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 76 et 318 sq.; T. Frymer-Kensky, *In the Wake of the Goddesses* (1992) 22 sq. et 72; C. Saporetti, *EVO* 16 (1993) 119 sq.; R.D. Wexler, *The Concepts of Mortality and Immortality in Ancient Mesopotamia* (Ph. D., Univ. of California 1993) 75-85 et 187-190; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 30-41 et 279 sq.; P. Michalowski in L. Milano (ed.), *Drinking in Ancient Societies* (Padoue, 1994) 41 sq.; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 33-45; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 157-190; Michalowski, *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 242 sq.; B. André-Salvini, dans: *Traces of Paradise: The Archaeology of Bahrain 2500 BC-3000 AD* (2000) 28-33; M. Stol, *CM* 14 (2000) 136 sq.; M.-F. Besnier, *CRRAI* 47 (2002) 60-64, 67, 69 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 204-208; B. Lion, *Âges d'or et paradis perdus dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: V. Pirenne-Delforge et

Ö. Tunca (ed.), *Représentations du temps dans les religions. Actes du Colloque organisé par le Centre d'Histoire des Religions de l'Université de Liège* (2003) 56-59; M. Tanret, *Mél. Klener* (2004) 176-183; K. Dickson, *JAOS* 125 (2005) 499-515; Dickson, *JNES* 66 (2007) 1-32; D. Katz, *BiOr.* 64 (2007) 568-589; ead., *BiOr.* 65 (2008) 320-342; P. Attinger, *NABU* 2008/71; L. Bachelot, *Mém. Bottéro* (2009) 36-39; B. Gadotti, *JAOS* 129 (2009) 74-76; N. Postgate, *Mém. Black* 237-243.; J. Scurlock, *NABU* 2010/31; C. Wilcke, dans: P. Gemeinhardt und A. Zgoll (ed.), *Weltkonstruktionen (Orientalische Religionen in der Antike* 5, 2010) 9-13; V. Grandpierre, *Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone* (2012) 32-40; P. Espak, dans: T. Kulmar und R. Schmitt (ed.), *Ideas of Man in the Conceptions of the Religions* (2012) 61-63; B.F. Batto, *In the Beginning: Essays on Creation Motifs in the Ancient Near East and the Bible* (2013) 56-65; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013)* 80-83; M. Guichard/L. Marti, dans: C. Frevel/C. Nihan (ed.), *Purity and the Forming of Religious Traditions in the Ancient Mediterranean World and Ancient Judaism* (2013) 60-65; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Heurs et malheurs du jardinier dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: D. Barbu et al. (ed.), *Mondes clos, cultures et jardins* (2013) 68-72, 79 sq. et 337-340; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 37-40, 50; J.C. Johnson, *BBVO* 23 (2014) 11-55 passim; G. Marchesi, *Kaskal* 11 (2014) 47-56; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 181-186; U. Steinert, dans: J.Z. Wee (ed.), *The comparable body: analogy and metaphor in ancient Mesopotamian, Egyptian, and Greco-Roman medicine (Studies in Ancient Medicine* 49, 2017) 275-357 (Enki et Ninḫursaĝa: pp. 314-316); N.W. Visser, *Enki's omzwervingen*, 2017; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 124-126; L.M. Pryke, dans: K.H. Keimer/G. Davis (ed.), *Register and Modes of Communication in the Ancient Near East [...] (2018)* 214, 216; N.W. Visser, *ENKI and NINHURSAĜA: a REHABILITATION*, 2018 (résumé de Visser 2017, téléchargeable à l'adresse http://enki-and-ninhursag.com/en_US/); B. Böck, *Medicina nei Secoli* 30 (2018) 505-530; M. Ceravolo, *Historia Religionum* (2019) 119-137; R.M. van Dijk-Coombes, *Scriptura* 119 (2020) 4-6.

Enki und Ninmah (3.1.d): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 151-166; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 188-198; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 386-401; ETC SL 1.1.2 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 407-415 (cf. aussi 117 sq.); W.G. Lambert, *MC* 16 (2013) 330-345, 498-509 et pl. 57-63 (édition); T. Rodin, *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess: An Interpretation of Her Myths* (2014) 44-46, 48-50, 111 sq., 229-298, 338-342 (trad.); M. Ceccarelli, *Enki und Ninmah. Eine mythische Erzählung in sumerischer Sprache (= ORA* 16, 2016) (édition). — Cf. A. Draffkorn Kilmer, *AOAT* 25 (1976) 265-270; M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile* 64 [1988]) 24-26; I.M. Kikawada, *Iraq* 45 (1983) 43-45 (réédité dans R.S. Hess/D.T. Tsumura [ed.], *I Studied Inscriptions from Before the Flood [= Sources for Biblical and Theological Study* 4, Winona Lake, 1994] 169-174); R. Borger, *Or.* 54 (1985) 18-22; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 31-37; H. Limet, *Mél. Sjöberg* 360 sq. et 364; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 322 sq.; W.G. Lambert, *CRRAI* 38 (1991, ed. 1992) 129-135; T. Frymer-Kensky, *In the Wake of the Goddesses* (1992) 72 sq.; H. Sauren, *Mél. Hallo* 198-208; C. Saporetti, *EVO* 16 (1993) 120 sq.; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 26-29 et 278 sq.; P. Michalowski in L. Milano (ed.), *Drinking in Ancient Societies (Padoue, 1994)* 41 sq.; M. Dietrich, *AOAT* 240 (1995) 58-60; W. Heimpel, *RIA* 8/7-8 (1997) 558; J. Klein, *The Context of Scripture* I 516-518 (traduction partielle); R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies* 1998) 191-211; M. Stol, *CM* 14 (2000) 80/82 et 109 sq.; M.

Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 197 sq.; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 16 (2004) 24-26; id., *MARG* 17 (2005) 141-144; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 29-34; A. Westenholz, *Mél. J.G. Westenholz* (2010) 201-204; P. Espak, dans: T. Kulmar und R. Schmitt (ed.), *Ideas of Man in the Conceptions of the Religions* (2012) 46 sq., 54-56; U. Steinert, *CM* 44 (2012) 50 sq.; A. Zgoll, in: K. Schmid (ed.), *Schöpfung* (= *Themen der Theologie* 4, 2012) 46-49; J.M. Asher-Greve, *OBO* 259 (2013) 141-145; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 83-85; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 46-50 et 268-283 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 48-53 et 293-309; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 40-43, 53 sq.; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 162-164 et 174 sq.; S. Pittl, *Kaskal* 12 (2015) 467-483; Kaĝnici, G., *Tarih İncelemeri Dergisi* 33 (2018) 429-450; I. Peled, *AOAT* 435 (2016) 84 sq., L. Verderame, *Mél. Geller* (2018) 797 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 12; G. Matini/C. Sapoterri, *dubsar* 6 (2019) 173-179; L. Verderame, *Henoch* 41 (2019) 21 sq.; K. Maiwald, *Mesopotamische Schöpfungstexte in Ritualen [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 3, 2021) 367-385.

Enki und die Weltordnung (3.1.e): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 165-188; *ETCSL* 1.1.3 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 184-203; Vanstiphout, *Revue belge de philologie et d'histoire* 77 (1999) 5-51 (édition); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 121-145; Black et alii, *LAS* 215-225; R.E. Averbeck, dans: K. Lawson Younger Jr. (ed.), *The Context of Scripture IV* (2017) 340-351. — Cf. H. Limet, dans H. Limet/J. Ries (ed.) *Le mythe, son langage et son message* (Actes du colloque de Liège et Louvain-la-Neuve, 1981; ed. dans *Homo Religiosus* 9, 1983) 81-96; R.S. Falkowitz, *Entretiens sur l'antiquité classique* 30 (1984) 13 sqq.; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 38-56; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 319-321; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 402-420; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 39-44; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 23-26 et 278; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *CM* 7 (1997) 117-134; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 128-156; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 64-66; M. Stol, *CM* 14 (2000) 110-112; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 220; R.E. Averbeck, in: R.E. Averbeck/alii, *Life and Culture in the Ancient Near East* (2003) 26-61; id., *JAOS* 123 (2003) 757-771; M. Tanret, *Mél. Klener* (2004) 183-186; K. Dickson, *JAOS* 125 (2005) 502-504; A.M. Bagg, *Schriften der DWhG* 12 (2008) 216-218; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 79; C. Mittermayer, *OBO* 256 (2012) 243-258; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 134-145; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 97-99; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 194-200; P. Espak, *Studia Orientalia Tartuensia* 2019 37-42; A.M. Bagg, *dubsar* 17 (2020) 16 sq.

Enlil und Ninlil (3.1.f): J.S. Cooper, *JCS* 32 (1980) 175-188; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 167-180; Bottéro/ Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 105-115; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 421-434; *ETCSL* 1.2.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 165-173; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 171-179; J. Scurlock, *Nin* 4 (2003 [paru en 2006]) 61-103 (traduction commentée aux pp. 62-65); Black et alii, *LAS* 102-106; Attinger, *TTS* 2015; H. Steible, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 21-31 et 417. — Cf. A. Falkenstein, *ZA* 47 (1942) 194-197; S.N. Kramer, *Sumerian Mythology [...]* (1944, 1961) 43-47 et 114; T. Jacobsen, *JNES* 4 (1946)

130 sq. n. 8, 132-134; Kramer, *The Sumerians: Their History, Culture, and Character* (1963) 146 sq.; G.S. Kirk, *Myth: Its Meaning and Functions in Ancient and Other Cultures* (1970) 99-103; V. Afanasieva, *ZA* 70 (1980) 163-169; R.S. Falkowitz, *Entretiens sur l'antiquité classique* 30 (1984) 18 sqq.; Hall, *Nanna/Suen* 524-526 et 609 sq; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 37-43; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 316 sq.; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 37 sq.; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 42-47 et 280 sq.; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 47-63; Michalowski, *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 243 sq.; Cooper, *CRRA* 45/I (2001) 140 n. 44; J. Klein, *CRRAI* 45/I 283 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 203 sq.; D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) 37-39; B. Groneberg, *Die Götter des Zweistromlandes* (2004) 63-65 et 229 sq.; V. Van der Stede, *Lettres orientales* 12 (2007) 144 sq.; L. Bachelot, *Mém. Bottéro* (2009) 32-35; A. Gadotti, *JAOS* 129 (2009) 78-82; V. Grandpierre, *Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone* (2012) 25-29; A. Zgoll, *Mém. Hruška* (2011) 287-299; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2013) 111-114; A. Zgoll, *Fundamente des Lebens. Vom Potential altorientalischer Mythen*, dans: A. Zgoll und R.G. Kratz (ed.), *Arbeit am Mythos* (2013) 79-107; J.M. Asher-Greve, *OBO* 259 (2013) 145-148; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 87 sq.; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 29-33, 51 sq.; T. Rodin, *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess: An Interpretation of Her Myths* (2014) 221-227; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 37-41; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 95-97; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 220 sq.; L.M. Pryke, dans: K.H. Keimer/G. Davis (ed.), *Register and Modes of Communication in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2018) 211 sq. et 215 sq.; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 111-113 (à propos des ll.10-33); C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 505-508, 537 sq., 542 sq.; A. Zgoll, *Durch Tod zur Macht, selbst über den Tod. [...]*, dans: A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll (ed.), *Mythische Sphärenwechsel. Methodisch neue Zugänge zu antiken Mythen in Orient und Okzident* (= *Mythological Studies* 2 [2020]) 91.

Enlil und Sud (3.1.g): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 115-127; H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 174-183; *ETCSL* 1.2.2 (2000); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 180-190; Black et alii, *LAS* 106-111; M. Fritz, dans: B. Heiningen (ed.), *An den Schwellen des Lebens. Zur Geschlechterdifferenz in Ritualen des Übergangs* (2008) 76-82. — Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *CRRAI* 33 (1986, ed. 1987) 169 sq.; C. Wilcke, *ib.* 180-185; C. Saporetti, *EVO* 16 (1993) 117-119; P. Michalowski, *NABU* 1994/51; *id.*, *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 243 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 216; B. Groneberg, *Die Götter des Zweistromlandes* (2004) 65-67; V. Grandpierre, *Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone* (2012) 30 sq.; J.M. Asher-Greve, *OBO* 259 (2013) 145-148; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 29, 33-37, 52; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 121-124; L.M. Pryke, dans: K.H. Keimer/G. Davis (ed.), *Register and Modes of Communication in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2018) 210 sq. et 214; C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 487-489; A. Cavigneaux, *RA* 114 (2020) 70-74.

Enmerkar und der 'Herr' (e n) von Aratta (3.1.h): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 275-319; *ETCSL* 1.8.2.3 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 84-112; *id.*, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta* (= *Writings from the Ancient World* 20, 2004) 49-96; P. Attinger, *TTS* 2015; C. Mittermayer, *Enmerkara und der Herr von Arata. Ein*

ungleicher Wettstreit (= OBO 239, 2009) (édition); ead., TUAT NF 8 (2015) 3-24; Mittermayer, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 169-201 et 421. — Cf. O.R. Gurney, *AfO* 25 (1974/1977) 170 sq.; B. Alster, *BBVO* 2 (1983) 39-74, surtout 57 sq.; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *Mél. Sjöberg* 515-524; C. Uehlinger, *OBO* 101 (1990) 409-429; B.F. Batto, dans: K.L. Younger et alii (ed.), *The Biblical Canon in Comparative Perspective. Scripture in Context IV* (1991) 42-45 et 48-50; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 76 sq. et 146-151; Gurney, *NABU* 1992/54; Th. Jacobsen dans M. Fishbane/*alii* (ed.), "Sha³arei Talmon". *Studies in the Bible, Qumran, and the Ancient Near East Presented to Shemaryahu Talmon*, Winona Lake, 1992, pp. 403-416; Vanstiphout, *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 247-264; C. Zaccagnini, *AoF* 20 (1993) 34-42; Vanstiphout, *RA* 88 (1994) 135-154; id., *OLP* 26 (1995) 5-20; id., *CM* 6 (1996) 162; Jacobsen, *The Context of Scripture I* 547-550 (traduction partielle); J.-J. Glassner, *Écrire à Sumer* (2000) 27-44; J. Klein, *Studi Cagni* (2000) 563-584; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 210-212; C. Wilcke, in: M. Brehl/K. Platt (ed.), *Feindschaft* (2003) 109-111; C. Schmidt, *BaM* 36 (2005) 54 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuhgiranna* (2006) 42-47; I. Good, *Invisible Exports in Aratta: Enmerkar and the Three Tasks*, dans: C. Gillis and M.-L. B. Nosch (ed.), *Ancient Textiles: Production, Craft and Society. Proceedings of the First International Conference on Ancient Textiles, held at Lund, Sweden, and Copenhagen, Denmark, on March 9-23, 2003*, Oxbow Books 2007, 179-184; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 24-26/47-49; J. Keetman, *NABU* 2010/63; id., *ZA* 100 (2010) 16-25; C. Mittermayer, *CRRAI* 53/1 (2010) 377-387; B.F. Batto, *In the Beginning: Essays on Creation Motifs in the Ancient Near East and the Bible* (2013) 65-75; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 81-84; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 108-112; F. Hazelton, *Three Kings of Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia* (2013) 10-32 (renarration); J. Cale Johnson, *CHANE* 68 (2014) 47-49, 59-61; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 194-198; D. Katz, *CRRAI* 60 (2017) 201-210 passim; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 105 sq., 113 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 11.

Fluch über Akkade (3.1.i): J.-M. Durand, *AEPHE* 1974/1975, 154-181; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 359-374; *ETCSL* 2.1.5 (1998-1999); Black et alii, *LAS* 116-125; Attinger, *TTS* (2009, actualisé en 2015); J.L. Dahl/R.K. Englund, *CDLI* (2014-2015); A. Cavigneaux, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 319-335 et 436; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 350-358, index p. 430; P. Attinger, *TUAT NF* 9 (2020) 41-54; B.R. Foster, dans K. Polinger Foster, *A Mesopotamian Miscellany* (2020) 47-57. — Cf. J.-J. Glassner, *BBVO* 5 (1986) passim, surtout 66-77; D.O. Edzard, *Mél. Sjöberg* 99-105; F. Pomponio, *Formule di maledizione [...]* (1990) 83-87; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 267-275 et 370 sq.; J.S. Cooper, *HANES* 5 (1993) 16 sq.; Rollinger, *Frühformen* 8-29 et passim; M. Liverani, *HANES* 5 56-59; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 33-35; P. Steinkeller, *JNES* 52 (1993) 142; P. Mander, *Mél. Moscati* (1996) I 261-264; J. Cooper, *CRRAI* 45/I (2001) 132 sq. et 138-142; J.S. Cooper, *JCS* 38 (2006) 39-42; 45; F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 171-175; P. Attinger, *NABU* 2007/46; J.G. Westenholz, *Mél. Sigrist* (2008) 251-253; ead., dans: D. Konstan and K.A. Raaflaub (ed.), *Epic and History* (2010) 33; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.), *The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600* (2011) 16 sq.; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 94-96; J.C. Johnson, *CHANE* 68 (2014) 47 sq. avec n. 13, 51-59; C. Wilcke, *CRRAI* (2015) 38-41; M.R. Bachvarova, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), *The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy* (2016) 43-46; S. Fink, *AOAT* 390/4 (2016) 124 sq.; P.

Steinkeller, *SANER* 15 (2017) 79 sq.; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 101-106.

Flut (3.1.j): Th. Jacobsen, *JBL* 100/4 (1981) 513-529; S.N. Kramer, *AnSt.* 33 (1983) 115-121; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 145-150; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 564-567; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 448-458; Jacobsen, *The Context of Scripture I* 513-515; *ETCSL* 1.7.4 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 204-209; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 146-151; Black et alii, *LAS* 212-215; J. Peterson, *JCS* 70 (2018) 37-51 (version d'Ur). — Cf. M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988])* 65-68; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 71; A. Cavigneaux, *SMEA* 31 (1993) 97-101; J.R. Davila, *JNES* 54 (1995) 202 sq.; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 20 (2010) 46 sq.; H.S. Kvanvig, *Primeval History: Babylonian, Biblical and Enochic [...]* (2011) 84-89; Y.S. Chen, *JANER* 12 (2012) 179-183; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 118-121; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 53-55 et 291-295 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 55-57 et 318-323; I. Finkel, *The Ark Before Noah: Decoding the Story of the Flood* (2014) 90-92; A. Zgoll, *Ash-sharq* 1 (2017) 155-161.

Gilgameš und Akka (3.1.k): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 345-355; G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 307-311 et 399-401; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 549-559; D. Katz, *Gilgamesh and Akka* (= *Library of Oriental Texts* 1, Groningen, 1993) (édition); R.J. Tournay/A. Shaffer, *LAPO* 15 (1994) 282-291 (trad.); ; Katz, *The Context of Scripture I* 550-552; H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 47-54; A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 143-148, second edition (2020) 99-105; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.1 (2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 99-104, (2019) 104-109; H. Neumann, *Gilgamesch und Akka*, dans: S. Franke (ed.), *Als die Götter Mensch waren* (2013) 91-95 et 120 sq.; H. Waetzoldt, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 273-281 et 434 sq. — Cf. W.G. Lambert, *Or.* 49 (1980) 339 sq.; P. Michalowski, *BSOAS* 45 (1982) 577-578; J. Klein, *JAOS* 103 (1983) 201-204; Vanstiphout, *OLP* 17 (1986) 33-50; id., *AulOr.* 5 (1987) 129-141; id., *NABU* 1989/99; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 162-166; id., *Rendiconti Morali, Accademia dei Lincei serie 9, vol. 5/1* (1994) 47-85; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 17-22; T. Marik, *ArOr.* 66 (1998) 265-269; G.J. Selz, *AOAT* 253 (1998) 313-319; C. Wilcke, *AOAT* 253, 457-485; Wu Yuhong, *NABU* 1998/103; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 45-48; P. Michalowski, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 72 (1999) 254; Vanstiphout, *JAOS* 119 (1999) 293-296; M. Civil, *AulOr.* 17-18 (1999-2000) 179-189; R.T. Ridley, *Or.* 69 (2000) 341-367; J.-D. Forest, *L'Epopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 218-223; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 8 sq.; R. Jiménez Zamudio, *Antología de textos sumerios* (2003) 52-55; M. Lang, *AOAT* 325 (2005) 497-508; J. Sanmartín, *Epopeya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 312-314; 328; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Enshūgiranna* (2006) 60-62; S. Anthonioz, *Semitica et Classica* 2 (2009) 17-19; M. Guichard, *Initiation à la littérature sumérienne, Annuaire de l'Ecole pratique des hautes études (EPHE), Section des sciences historiques et philologiques* 140 (2007-2008) 24-32; J. Keetman, *Babel und Bibel* 6 (2012) 15-30; J.C. Johnson, *AVO* 15 (2015) 169-172; S. Franke, dans: M. Grohmann (ed.), *Identität und Schrift. Fortschreibungsprozesse als Mittel religiöser Identitätsbildung* (2017) 20-22; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 158 sq.; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 131-136; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 32 sq.

Gilgameš, Enkidu und die Unterwelt (1.3.1): S.N. Kramer, *The Sumerians* 197-205; G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 329-342 et 409-412; R.J. Tournay/A. Shaffer, *LAPO* 15 (1994) 248-274; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.4 (1998-2000); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 175-195, second edition (2020) 131-145; D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 129-143, (2019) 109-125; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 439-457; Black et alii, *LAS* 31-40; A. Gadotti, "Gilgameš, Enkidu and the Netherworld" and the Sumerian Gilgameš Cycle, Ph. D. diss., The John Hopkins University 2005 (édition); Attinger, *TTS* (2008-2009, actualisé en 2015); Attinger, *TUAT NF* 8 (2015) 24-37; Attinger, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 297-316 et 435 sq. — Cf. B. Alster, *RA* 68 (1974) 55-60 et *ASJ* 5 (1983) 1-16; A. Koefoed, *ASJ* 5 (1983) 17-23; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/1* (1986) 36-45; J. Tropper, *WO* 17 (1986) 19-24; J. Bauer, *OPSNKF* 11 (1989) 21 sqq.; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 82 sq.; J. Tropper, *AOAT* 223 (1989) 62-69; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumero-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 19-37; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 173-177, 312 et 330 sq.; Th. Jacobsen, *Mél. Hallo* 120-123; D.O. Edzard, *BCSMS* 27 (1994) 12 sq.; K. Hecker, *TUAT III/4* (1994) 739-744; E. Frahm, *JCS* 51 (1999) 76-78; V.K. Afanasieva, *VDI* 233 (2000) 53-63; A. Cavigneaux/F. Al-Rawi, *Iraq* 62 (2000) 1-19; Pettinato, *Studi Cagni* (2000) 875-878; J.-D. Forest, *L'Epopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 196-211; J. Klein, dans: T. Abusch (ed.), *Riches Hidden in Secret Places: Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Memory of Thorkild Jacobsen* (2002) 187-201; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 194-196; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 12-14, 45-54, 743-777 et 898-905 (édition des ll. 172-fin); D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) passim (index des lignes discutées p. 481); Pettinato, *I miti degli inferi assiro-babilonesi* (2003) 137 sq., 158-160 et 162-167; D.O. Edzard, *OBO* 160/4 (2004) 494 et n. 34, 558 n. 267, 605-609; B. Alster, *Wisdom of Ancient Sumer* (2005) 339-341; F. Joannès, *Ktéma* 30 (2005) 81-83; J. Sanmartín, *Epopeya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 322-326; 329 sq.; A.J. Ferrara, *CM* 35 (2006) 47-66; R. Rollinger, *Nikephoros* 19 (2006) 9-44 passim, surtout 15-24 et 33-38; J. Keetman, *BiOr.* 64 (2007) 5-31.; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* 442-449 (ll. 14-26 //); V. Van der Stede, *Lettres orientales* 12 (2007) 118-121; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 26 sq.; R. Rollinger, *JCS* 60 (2008) 15-23; J.A. Lynch, *Gilgamesh's Ghosts: The Dead, Textual Variation, and the Mesopotamian Scribal Tradition*. Ph. D., Univ. of California 2010; Maul, S.M., *Himmelfahrt und Abstieg in die Unterwelt — altorientalische Mythe von Jenseitsreisen*, dans: E. Hornung und A. Schweizer (ed.), *Jenseitsreisen, Eranos 2009 und 2010* (2011) 246-270 (version akkadienne de GEN: 265-270); Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 87-90; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 42-46 et 258-267 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 44-48 et 282-292; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Heurs et malheurs du jardinier dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: D. Barbu et al. (ed.), *Mondes clos, cultures et jardins* (2013) 80-82 et 340 sq.; A. Annus and M. Sarv, *Melammu Symposia* 7 (2015) 285-296, surtout 289-294; A. Jordanova, *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten*. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015) 361-369; N.A. Corfù, *AOAT* 439 (2016) 37-46; S.J. Milstein, *Tracking the Master Scribe: Revision through Introduction in Biblical and Mesopotamian Literature* (2016) 136-144; J.A. Lynch, *OBO SA* 40 (2018) 241-244; P. Steinkeller, *JANEH* 5 (2018) 156-172 passim; A. Gadotti/A. Kleinerman, *Mél. Sasson* (2020) 138-143 (nouveau duplicat); J. Keetman, *BiOr.* 77 (2020) 218-222; T. Simkó, *JCS* 72 (2020) 28-30; K. Maiwald, *Mesopotamische Schöpfungstexte in Ritualen [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 3, 2021) 353-366.

Gilgameš und der Himmelsstier (3.1.m): G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 324-328 et 408; A. Cavigneaux/F.N.H. Al-Rawi, *RA* 87 (1993) 97-129 (édition); *ETCSL* 1.8.1.2 (1998); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 166-175, second edition (2020) 122-131; D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 120-127, (2019) 138-146; . Klein/Y. Sefati, *From the Workshop of the Mesopotamian Scribe: Literary and Scholarly Texts from the Old Babylonian Period* (2019) 5-74 (édition partielle). — Cf. C. Wilcke, *Voix de l'opposition* 57-59; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 177-179; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 57 sq.; A.R. George, *CRRAI* 47 (2002) 144-149; J.-D. Forest, *L'Epopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 215-218; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 222 sq.; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 11 sq.; B. Alster, *PIHANS* 100 (2004) 34 sq.; A. Gadotti, *CM* 35 (2006) 67-83 passim.; S. Anthonioz, *Semitica et Classica* 2 (2009) 21 sq.; S. Ponchia, *StOr.* 106 (2009) 399-407; A.R. George, *Mém. Black* 101-115; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2013) 173-178; S. Franke, dans: M. Grohmann (ed.), *Identität und Schrift. Fortschreibungsprozesse als Mittel religiöser Identitätsbildung* (2017) 24-29 (versions sum. et akk.); P. Steinkeller, *JANEH* 5 (2018) 158 sq.; B.R. Foster, dans K. Polinger Foster, *A Mesopotamian Miscellany* (2020) 4 sq.; J. Klein/Y. Sefati, *Mél. Sasson* (2020) 175-185.

Gilgameš und Huwawa (3.1.n) 1. **version A**: D.O. Edzard, *ZA* 80 (1990) 165-203 et *ZA* 81 (1991) 165-233 (édition); G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 312-323 et 401-408; Edzard, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 540-549; id., Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-historische Klasse, *Sitzungsberichte Jahrgang 1993, Heft 4* (München, 1993) 35-45; R.J. Tournay/A. Shaffer, *LPO* 15 (1994) 292-305; H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 55-67; A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 149-161, second edition (2020) 105-116; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.5 (1999-2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 104-115, (2019) 125-138; Black et alii, *LAS* 343-352; W.H.Ph. Römer, *UF* 37 (2005) 517-555; Delnero, *Variation 2396-2474* (partition); D.E. Fleming/S.J. Milstein, *CM* 39 (2010) passim, surtout 182-195; E. Smith, *The Sumerian Mythographic Tradition and Its Implications for Genesis 1-11*, PhD diss., University of Bristol and Trinity College 2012, 108-129 (translittération, traduction et très bref commentaire); Edzard, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 283-295 et 435. — Cf. J. Hansman, *Iraq* 38 (1976) 23-35; N. Forsyth, *ASJ* 3 (1981) 13-29; M. deJong Ellis, *AfO* 28 (1981-1982) 123-131; A. Shaffer, *JAOS* 103 (1983) 307-313; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/5 (1989) 713-715; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 166-173; B. Alster, *BSOAS* 55 (1992) 1-8; id., *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 65-69; Edzard, *BCSMS* 27 (1994) 9 sq.; D. Katz, *NABU* 1995/29; G. Steiner, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 187-215; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 48-53; A. Cavigneaux/F. Al-Rawi, *Iraq* 62 (2000) 5 sq.; J. Klein/K. Abraham, *HANE/M-III/3* (2000) 63-73; J.-D. Forest, *L'Epopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 211-215; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 227 sq.; M. Civil, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 77-86; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 9 sq. 2; J. Sanmartín, *Epopeya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 314-319; 328 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuĝgiranna* (2006) 62-64; S. Anthonioz, *Semitica et Classica* 2 (2009) 19-21; P. Michalowski, dans: K.A. Raaflaub and R.J.A. Talbert (ed.), *Geography and Ethnography* (2010) 160 sq./165 n. 13 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *OBO* 245 (2010) 135-164 passim; J. Taylor, *Mém. Black* 351-360; L. Verderame, *AOAT* 441 (2017) 285-287 et 294-296. **version B**: Edzard, Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-historische Klasse, *Sitzungsberichte Jahrgang 1993, Heft 4* 1-61 (édition); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 162-166, second

edition (2020) 105 sq. et 117-122; ETCSL 1.8.1.5.1 (1999-2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 115-120; D.E. Fleming/S.J. Milstein, *CM* 39 (2010) passim, surtout 196-205. — Cf. A. Ganter, *NABU* 1995/41; G. Steiner, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 187-215; id., *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 373-376; G. Marchesi, *Studi Cagni* (2000) 673-684; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 220 sq.; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 10 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *OBO* 245 (2010) 135-164 passim; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2013) 89-93; N. Samet, *Biblica* 96 (2015) 379-382; L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 369-373; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 118 sq.

Gilgameš in der Unterwelt (3.1.o): G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 343-347 et 412 sq.; ETCSL 1.8.1.3 (1998-2000); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 195-208, second edition (2020) 122-131; A. Cavigneaux/F.N.H. Al-Rawi, *Gilgameš et la Mort* (= *Textes de Tell Haddad VI*), *CM* 19 (2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 143-154, (2019) 148-158, (2019) 109-125; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 458-476; N. Veldhuis, *JCS* 53 (2001) 133-148. — Cf. R. Jestin, *Syria* 33 (1956) 113-118; J. van Dijk, *HSAO* 1 (1967) 248-251; Th. Jacobsen, *Mesop.* 8 (1980) 19-24; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/1 (1986) 34-36; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerio-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 71-76; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 181-183; A. Cavigneaux/F. al-Rawi, *Iraq* 55 (1993) 93; R. Rollinger, *Nikephoros* 7 (1994) 37 sq.; J.-D. Forest, *L'Épopée de Gilgameš et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 221-226; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 221 sq.; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 14-17; D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) passim (index des lignes discutées p. 480); G. Marchesi, *Or.* 73 (2004) 156-161; C. Wilcke, *NABU* 2004/98; J. Sanmartín, *Epopeya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 326 sq.; 330; A. Zgoll, *AOAT* 333 (2006) 101-104; J. Keetman, *JNES* 67 (2008) 164 sq.; S. Anthonioz, *OBO* 257 (2012) 82-92; W. Sallaberger, *Der Tod des göttlichen Königs [...]*, dans A. Lang/P. Marinković (Hg.), *Bios – Cultus – (Im)mortalitas. Zu Religion und Kultur – Von den biologischen Grundlagen bis zu Jenseitsvorstellungen. Beiträge der interdisziplinären Kolloquien vom 10.– 11. März 2006 und 24.–25. Juli 2009 in der Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München. Internationale Archäologie – Arbeitsgemeinschaft, Symposium, Tagung, Kongress; Band 16, 127-130; id., Der Tod des göttlichen Königs [...]*, in: M. Fieger und M. Weder (ed.), *Krankheit und Sterben. Ein interprofessioneller Dialog* (= *Das Alte Testament im Dialog* 6, 2012) 245-271 (*Gilgameš in der Unterwelt: 257-265*); Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 106-108; N. Artemov, *CRRAI* 55 (2014) 38-41; Jordanova, A., *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig* (2015) 357-361; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 153-159; Sallaberger, W., *Tuna el-Gebel* 9 (2019) 99-102.

Götterreisen (3.1.p): Cf. en général R. Mayer-Opificius, *Mitteilungen für Anthropologie und Religionsgeschichte* 15 (2000; paru en 2003) 81-102; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 305 sq.; K. Wagensonner, *WZKM* 97 (2001) 541-559; id., *Götterreisen* (2005).

Enkis Reise nach Nippur (3.1.p 1) =(!) **Eridu-Hymne** (3.2.3.b): Castellino, *TSA* 209-214; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 142-150; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 69-74; ETCSL 1.1.4 (1999); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 358-364;

Black et alii, LAS 330-333; Delnero, Variation 2239-2290 (partition); F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 225-231; M. Ceccarelli, OBO 256 (2012) 89-118 (édition; v. id., NABU 2013/40); J. Bauer, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 365-372 et 437. — Cf. G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 332 sq.; J. Bottéro, *La plus vieille Religion. En Mésopotamie* (1998) 278-282 (traduction partielle); R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 81-99; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 198; Wagensooner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 81-91; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 85; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 99 sq.; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Mythos* 11 (2017) 40 sq.; P. Espak, *Studia Orientalia Tartuensia* 2019 42-44; K. Maiwald, *Mesopotamische Schöpfungstexte in Ritualen [...] (= Mythological Studies 3, 2021) 257-279.*

Nannas Reise nach Nippur (3.1.p 2): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/2 (1987) 175-189; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 128-142; *ETCSL* 1.5.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 337-351; Black et alii, LAS 147-154. — Cf. C. Wilcke, *AfO* 24 (1973) 2-6; A.J. Ferrara, *RA* 68 (1974) 169-172; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 364 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 227 sq.; Wagensooner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 35-55.

Gudam (3.1.q): W.H.Ph. Römer, *BiOr.* 48 (1991) 363-378 (édition); *ETCSL* 1.3.4 (1998-2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 127-129; B. Alster, *PIHANS* 100 (2004) 21-45 (édition). — Cf. A. Gadotti, *GEN* (2005) 166-170; ead., *CM* 35 (2006) 67-83.

Inanna und Bilulu (3.1.r): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 330-337; *ETCSL* 1.4.4 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 396-403. — Cf. T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumero-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 59-63; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 159; K. Sonik, *JAOS* 132 (2012) 389 sq.; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 47-51, 55 sq.; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 315 sq.; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 117 sq. (à propos des ll. 98-110).

Inanna und Ebih (3.1.s): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 219-229; P. Attinger, *ZA* 88 (1998) 164-195 (édition); *ETCSL* 1.3.2 (1998-1999); Betty De Shong Meador, *Inanna, Lady of Largest Heart* (2000) 89-113 et 201-203; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 284-294; Black et alii, LAS 334-338; Delnero, Variation 2291-2359 (partition); Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015); Attinger, *TUAT* NF 8 (2015) 37-45; Attinger, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 353-363 et 437; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 341-347, index p. 432; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 87-93. — Cf. Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 47-49; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 232-257; A. Zgoll, *HANE/M* III/2 (2000) 83-86 et 89 sq.; J. Cooper, *CRRAI* 45/I (2001) 135 n. 20 et 143 avec n. 58; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 223-225; F. Karahashi, *JNES* 63 (2004) 111-118; M. Jaques, *ZA* 94 (2004) 202-225; P. Delnero, *Mél. Eichler* (2011) 123-149; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 200-206; L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 364-366; I. Peled, *AOAT* 435 (2016) 66-68; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 133 sq.; A. Perdibon, *LAOS* 11 (2019) 63-66; ead., *Distant Worlds Journal* 4 (2020) 127-131.

Inanna und Enki (3.1.t): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 230-256; ETCSL 1.3.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 307-356. — Cf. B. Alster, *ZA* 64 (1975) 20-34; H. Waetzoldt, *BiOr.* 32 (1975) 382-384; H. Limet, *Mél. Sjöberg* 361 sq. et 364; J.-J. Glassner, *CRRAI* 35 (1988, ed. 1992) 55-86; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 362-364; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 44 sq.; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 41-44; G. Farber, *JNES* 54 (1995) 287-292; id., *The Context of Scripture I* 522-526 (traduction partielle); R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 100-127; G.J. Selz, *Mél. Dux* (2003) 251-254; Wagensohn, *Götterreisen* (2005) 191-194; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuĝiranna* (2006) C.E. Barrett, *JANER* 7 (2007) 21 sq.; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 29-45, 272-275; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 281-288; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 79 sq.; G.J. Selz, *Mél. de Meis* (2014) 64 sq.; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek (ed.), *De la steppe au bateau céleste ou comment Inanna accomplit son destin entre mythe et rite*, dans: N. Belayche/V. Pirenne-Delforge, *Fabriquer du divin. Constructions et ajustements de la représentation des dieux dans l'Antiquité* (2015) 21-40 passim; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 100-102; I. Peled, *AOAT* 435 (2016) 68-71; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 91-94; G.B. Selz, *Melammu* 9 (2018) 431-433; P. Espak, *Studia Orientalia Tartuensia* 2019 44-46; J. Keetman, *BiOr.* 77 (2020) 215-218.

Inannas Gang zur Unterwelt (3.1.u): D. Wolkstein/S.N. Kramer, *Inanna, Queen of Heaven and Earth [...]* (1983) 51-85 et 206; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 205-232; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 276-295; D.D. Jones, *She spoke to them with a stormy heart: The politics of reading ancient (or other) narrative* (Ph. D., Univ. of Minnesota 1993) passim, surtout 1 sq., 102-139, 189-229 (traduction), 230-266, 271-275; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 458-495; ETCSL 1.4.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 210-228; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 260-283; Black et alii, *LAS* 65-76; H. Waetzoldt, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 375-398 et 437-441. — Cf. Kramer, *The Sacred Marriage Rite: Aspects of Faith, Myth, and Ritual in Ancient Sumer* (1969) 108-119 et 154-156 (trad. en français par J. Bottéro dans S.N. Kramer, *Le mariage sacré à Sumer et Babylone* [1983] 136-146 et 168-170, traduction en espagnol par M. Molina dans S.N. Kramer, *El Matrimonio Sagrado en la Antigua Sumer. Traducción y adaptación de Manuel Molina [= Colección: Estudios Orientales 11, 1999] 128-138 et 141); A. Draffkorn Kilmer, UF 3 (1971) 299-308; D. Irvin, AOAT 32 (1978) 38 sq.; V. Afanasieva, ZA 70 (1980) 161-169; S.N. Kramer, PAPS 124 (1980) 299-312; id., BCSMS 4 (1982) 26-32; G. Buccellati, SMS 4/3 (1982) 3-7; W. Burkert, OBO 48 (1982) 66-68; W. Heimpel, SMS 4/3 9-13; A.R. George, JCS 37 (1985) 109-113; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumero-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 7-18; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 327-330; R.D. Wexler, *The Concepts of Mortality and Immortality in Ancient Mesopotamia* (Ph. D., Univ. of California 1993) 157-182; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 49-55; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 17-26 et 246 sq.; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 65-98; D. Katz, *ZA* 85 (1995) 221-233; B. Alster, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 1-18; Katz, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 93-102; W. Heimpel, *RIA* 8/7-8 (1997) 556 sq.; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 258-291; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 128-138 et 141; J. Cooper, *CRRAI* 45/I (2001) 143 sq.; T.N.D. Mettinger, *The Riddle of Resurrection [...]* (=*

Coniectanea Biblica Old Testament Series 50, 2001), 187-190; P. Lapinkivi, CRRAI 47 (2002) 327-335 passim; M. Streck, Or. 71 (2002) 227-229; M.M. Fritz, AOAT 307 (2003) 102-104; D. Katz, The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources (2003) passim, surtout 251-287 (index des lignes discutées p. 482); Pettinato, I miti degli inferi assiro-babilonesi (2003) 135-137; D.O. Edzard, OBO 160/4 (2004) 495-497, 600 sq.; B. Groneberg, Die Götter des Zweistromlandes 181-184; Lapinkivi, SAAS 15 (2004) 189-194; Wagensonner, Götterreisen (2005) 195-198; A.J. Ferrara, CM 31 (2006) 127-138; C.E. Barrett, JANER 7 (2007) 20 sqq. passim.; V. Van der Stede, Lettres orientales 12 (2007) 129-147 passim; A.J. Ferrara, Mél. Abusch (2010) 27-47 passim; P. Lapinkivi, SAACT 6 (2010) 35-93 passim (comparaison avec La descente d'Ištar.); J.A. Lynch, Gilgamesh's Ghosts: The Dead, Textual Variation, and Mesopotamian Scribal Tradition (Ph. D., Univ. of California 2010) 191-201; I. Slobodzianek, Mythos 4 n.s. (2010) 32-35; B. Alster, OLA 189 (2011) 55-79; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek, dans: F. Gherchanoc et V. Huet (ed.), Vêtements antiques. S'habiller, se déshabiller dans les mondes anciens (2012) 135-148; V. Grandpierre, Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone (2012) 52-54; I. Slobodzianek, Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 147-155, 185-208, 265-271; K. Sonik, JAOS 132 (2012) 387-389; Broekema, Inanna (2013) 455-469; T.W.P.H. Tanaka, Dress and Identity in Old Babylonian Texts (Ph. D. diss., University of California, Berkeley, 2013) 20-65; A. Jordanova, Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015) 346-251; D. Katz, CRRAI 57 (2015) 64-71; I. Peled, AOAT 435 (2016) 50-55, 60-63; L.M. Pryke, Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World (2017) 101-110; G.J. Selz, AOAT 434 (2017) 277-290; R. Cabrera, JNSL 44 (2018) 41-79 passim; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme (2018) 130-132; B. Dedović, "Inanna's Descent to the Netherworld": A centennial survey of scholarship, artifacts, and translations, Bachelor of Arts diploma in History, University of Maryland, 2019; V. Muller, Mél. Rouault (2019) 212 sq.; C. Zgoll, Tractatus mythologicus [...] (= Mythological Studies 1 [2019]) 540 sq.; A. Zgoll, Durch Tod zur Macht, selbst über den Tod. [...], dans: A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll (ed.), Mythische Sphärenwechsel. Methodisch neue Zugänge zu antiken Mythen in Orient und Okzident (= Mythological Studies 2 [2020]) 83-159 passim; A. Zgoll, AOAT 460 (2020) 475-493; A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll, CM 50 (2020) 752-802 passim.

Inanna und Šukalle-tuda (3.1.v): Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 257-271; K. Volk, Inanna und Šukaletuda [...] (= SANTAG 3, 1995) (édition); ETCSL 1.3.3 (1999-2000); G. Pettinato, Mitologia sumerica (2001) 380-395; Black et alii, LAS 197-205; Attinger, TTS (2011, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. B. Alster, ZA 64 (1975) 30-34; Wilcke, Politik und Literatur 56 sq.; B. Hruška, ArOr. 66 (1998) 318-324; J. Cooper, CRRAI 45/I (2001) 142-144; G.J. Selz, JAC 16 (2001) 46-58; M.-F. Besnier, CRRAI 47 (2002) 60-64, 67, 69; M. Streck, Or. 71 (2002) 214-216; T. Marík, WZKM 93 (2003) 147-166; P. Lapinkivi, SAAS 15 (2004) 220-226; Volk, RIA 10/3-4 (2004) 288 sq.; J.L. Cooley, JANER 8 (2008) 75-98; id., Kaskal 5 (2008) 161-172; A. Gadotti, JAOS 129 (2009) 77 sq.; M. Guichard, Initiation à la littérature sumérienne, Annuaire de l'Ecole pratique des hautes études (EPHE), Section des sciences historiques et philologiques 140 (2007-2008) 21-24; L. Vacin, Šulgi of Ur: Life, Deeds, Ideology and Legacy of a Mesopotamian Ruler as Reflected primarily in Literary Texts (PhD, University of London, 2011) 107-110; Broekema, Inanna

(2013) 288-292; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East* [...] (2013) 160-173; C. Mittermayer, *ORA* 10 (2013) 35-38; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Heurs et malheurs du jardinier dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: D. Barbu et al. (ed.), *Mondes clos, cultures et jardins* (2013) 73-78 et 339 sq.; S. Parpola, *Melammu* 2014, 19; I. Slobodzianek, dans C. Bonnet et al. (ed.), *Puissances divines à l'épreuve du comparatisme: constructions, variations et réseaux relationnels* (= Bibliothèque de l'École des Hautes Études, sciences religieuses vol. 175, 2016) 265-272; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 71-83, 147 sq.; C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus* [...] (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 541 sq.; L. Verderame, *Ocula* 23 (2020) 19-26; A. Zgoll, *Durch Tod zur Macht, selbst über den Tod*. [...], dans: A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll (ed.), *Mythische Sphärenwechsel. Methodisch neue Zugänge zu antiken Mythen in Orient und Okzident* (= *Mythological Studies* 2 [2020]) 108-127.

Lugalbanda I (3.1.w): J. Black, *Reading Sumerian Poetry* (London 1998) 120-124 et 176-184; ETCSL 1.8.2.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 114-129; Black et alii, *LAS* 11-22; Vanstiphout, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta* (= *Writings from the Ancient World* 20, 2004) 99-131 et 159-163; C. Wilcke, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 206-220, 226-254, 422-427. — Cf. Hall, *Nanna/Suen* 529-533; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/1 (1986) 32-34; Wilcke, *RIA* 7, 1/2 (1987) 121-125 et 129 sq. s.v. Lugalbanda (bibl. p. 121); B. Alster, *Mél. Moran* 59-72 passim; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 153-157; Alster, *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 56-59; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *OLP* 26 (1995) 5-20; id., *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 397-412; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumera* (2001) 119 sq.; Vanstiphout, dans: T. Abusch (ed.), *Riches Hidden in Secret Places: Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Memory of Thorkild Jacobsen* (2002) 259-289 passim; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 200-202; Alster, *Iraq* 67 (2005) 61-71; D. Katz, *CM* 35 (2006) 110-113.; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuĝgiranna* (2006) 47-52; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 27 sq./49-51; F. Hazelton, *Three Kings of Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia* (2013) 33-53 (renarration de Lugalb. I et II); J.Z. Wee, *JNES* 73 (2014) 23-42 passim; Wilcke, *CRRAI* 57 (2015) 37 sq., 41-44 et 48; L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 366-369; A. Perdibon, *LAOS* 11 (2019) 48 sq.

Lugalbanda II (3.1.x): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 320-344; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 507-539; J. Black, *Reading Sumerian Poetry* (London 1998) passim (traduction pp. 58-64); ETCSL 1.8.2.2 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 130-149; Black et alii, *LAS* 22-31; Vanstiphout, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta* (= *Writings from the Ancient World* 20, 2004) 132-159 et 163-165; C. Wilcke, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 206-208, 220-226, 254-272, 427-434. — Cf. H. Sauren, *JEOL* 22 (1971/1972) 288-295; R.S. Falkowitz, *JAOS* 103 (1983) 103-114; Wilcke, *RIA* 7, 1/2 (1987) 125-130; B. Alster, *Mél. Moran* 59-72 passim; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 157-161; Alster, *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 56-59; D.O. Edzard, *BCSMS* 27 (1994) 11; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *OLP* 26 (1995) 5-20; ID, dans: T. Abusch (ed.), *Riches Hidden in Secret Places: Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Memory of Thorkild Jacobsen* (2002) 259-289 passim; J. Polonsky, *The Rise of the Sun God and the Determination of Destiny in Ancient Mesopotamia* (PhD., Univ. of Philadelphia 2002) 712-718; C. Schmidt, *BaM* 36 (2005) 55 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuĝgiranna* (2006) 51-56; F. Hazelton, *Three Kings of*

Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia (2013) 33-53 (renarration de Lugalb. I et II); L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 366-369.

Lugal(e) ud melambi nirgal (3.1.y): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 233-272; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 339-377; ETCSL 1.6.2 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 193-234; S. Seminara, *La versione accadica del Lugal-e* (= MVS 8, 2001); Black et alii, *LAS* 163-180; W. Heimpel/E. Salgues, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 33-67 et 417 sq. — Cf. Bruschweiler, *Inanna* 66-74; J. van Dijk, *RIA* 7, 1/2 (1987) 134-136; W. Heimpel, *JNES* 46 (1987) 309-317; Th. Jacobsen, *Mél. Sachs* 225-232; F. Pomponio, *Formule di maledizione [...]* (1990) 81-83; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 361 sq.; J. Black, *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 76-86; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 435-448; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 59 sq.; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 64-69; F.N.H. Al-Rawi, *Iraq* 57 (1995) 199-220 et appendice de A.R. George, *ibid.* 220-223.; K. Polinger Foster, *HANE/M-III/3* (2000) 23-39; G.J. Selz, *Mél. Haas* (2001) 383-393; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 217 sq.; C. Wilcke, in: M. Brehl/K. Platt (ed.), *Feindschaft* (2003) 113 sq.; F. Karahashi, *JEOL* 38 (2003-2004) 77-82; B. Groneberg, *Die Götter des Zweistromlandes* (2004) 81-85; Karahashi, *JNES* 63 (2004) 111-118; Seminara, *HSAO* 9 (2004) 243-250; Wagenossoner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 132-134; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 11-13; A.M. Bagg, *Schriften der DWhG* 12 (2008) 219 sq.; J.-D. Forest, *Mém. Bottéro* 42-45; 47-53 *passim*; M.J. Geller, *Mém. Black* 93-100; L. Feldt, *OLA* 189 (2011) 123-163; E. Frahm, *GMTR* 5 (2011) 117-119; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 77 sq.; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 50 et 284-286 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 53 et 310-313; K. Simkó, *JMC* 22 (2013) 24 *sqq. passim*; B. Böck, *The Healing Goddess Gula: Towards an Understanding of Ancient Babylonian Medicine* (= *CHANE* 67, 2014) 35-38; B.R. Foster, *CM* 46 (2014) 51-56; K. Simkó, *AoF* 41 (2014) 112-124; I.A. Sviatopolk-Czetvertynski, *AOAT* 401 (2014) 779-794; L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-364; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 90-95; J. Pace, *Mythopoeïa ou l'art de forger les "mythes" dans l'"aire culturelle" syro-mésopotamienne, méditerranéenne et indo-européenne* (= *SAAS* 27, 2018) *passim*, surtout 75-101, 106-112, 118 sq., 129-209; K. Wagenossoner, dans: J. Braarvig/M.J. Geller (ed.), *Multilingualism, Lingua Franca and Lingua Sacra* (Max Planck Research Library for the History and Development of Knowledge Studies 10, 2018) 248-256 et 280 sq.; M. Ramez, *NABU* 2018/110; A. Perdibon, *LAOS* 11 (2019) 47 sq.; M. Ramez, *Mél. Charpin* (2019) 862-866; W. Sallaberger, *Tuna el-Gebel* 9 (2019) 102-104; K. Simkó, *NABU* 2019/31; K. Maiwald, *Mesopotamische Schöpfungstexte in Ritualen [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 3, 2021) 332-352.

Martu-Mythos (3.1.z): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 430-437; W.H.Ph. Römer, *UF* 21 (1989) 319-334 (édition); S.N. Kramer, *Mél. Artzi* 11-27 (édition); Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 495-506; J. Klein, *CM* 7 (1997) 106-116 (translit. et traduction); ETCSL 1.7.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 298-303; . — Cf. J.-J. Glassner dans B.S. Lesko (ed.), *Women's Earliest Records [...]* (= *Brown Judaic Studies* 166, Atlanta, Georgia, 1989) p. 77; Klein, *Raphael Kutscher Memorial Volume* 93-106; R. Rollinger, *Nikephoros* 7 (1994) 18-23; Klein, in M. Malul (ed.), *Mutual Influences of Peoples and Cultures [...]* (Haifa, 1996) 83-96; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *NABU* 1996/54; *id.*, *OLA* 96 (1999) 461-474; M. Streck, *AOAT* 271/1 (2000) 70-75 et *Or.* 71 (2002) 208 sq.; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 92 sq.

Sargons-Legende (3.1.aa): V. Afanas²eva, *AoF* 14 (1987) 237-246; J.G. Westenholz, *CM* 7 (1997) 51-55 (VS 24 75); ETCSL 2.1.4 (1998); Black et alii, *LAS* 40-44; Attinger,

TTS (2010, actualisé en 2019); J.L. Dahl/R.K. Englund, CDLI P469678 (2014); B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 348-350. — Cf. J.S. Cooper dans A. Kort/S. Morschauser (ed.), *Biblical and Related Studies Presented to Samuel Iwry* (Winona Lake, 1985) 33-39; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/1* (1986) 31 sq.; B. Alster, *ZA* 77 (1987) 169-173; Cooper, *HANES* 5 (1993) 17 sq.; P. Attinger, *NABU* 1994/99; P. Gentili, *Studi Cagni* (2000) 355-373 passim, surtout 356-366; G. Cunningham, *OLA* 189 (2011) 81-96; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 44 sq.; P. Steinkeller, *SANER* 15 (2017) 182-186, 189-191.

Hymnen (3.2) P. Michalowski, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 72-73 (1999-2002) 255-262; C. Metcalf, *The Gods Rich in Praise: Early Greek and Mesopotamian Religious Poetry* (2015) passim, surtout 15-49 et 228-234.

Hendursanga-Hymne (3.2.1.a): ETCSL 4.06.1 (1999-2000); P. Attinger/M. Krebernik, *AOAT* 325 (2005) 21-104; F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 121-132; Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. D.O. Edzard/C. Wilcke, *AfO* 25 (1974/1977) 36; H. Sauren, *OLP* 10 (1979) 75-95; T. Frymer-Kensky, *In the Wake of the Goddesses* (1992) 50-59; L. Verderame, *AOAT* 441 (2017) 283-285 et 293 sq.

Inannas Erhöhung (3.2.1.b): R. Labat, *Les religions du Proche-Orient asiatique* (Paris, 1970) 240-247; Castellino, *TSA* 107-114.; D. Foxvog, *The Late Bilingual Exaltation of Ištar (Inannas Erhöhung)*, <https://www.academia.edu/4297790>, 2013. — Cf. W.G. Lambert, *Or.* 40 (1971) 91-95; E. von Weiher, *ADFU* 10 (1983) 136 Nr. 28; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy [...]* (2013) 130-140; N. Veldhuis, *AMD* 13 (2018) 183-206.

Innin šagurra (3.2.1.c): ETCSL 4.07.3 (1999); Betty De Shong Meador, *Inanna, Lady of Largest Heart* (2000) 114-167 et 204-206; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 336-341; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 79-87. — Cf. B. Alster, *NABU* 1990/100; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 59-63; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 45 sq.; P. Michalowski, in J. Braun et al. (ed.), *Written on Clay and Stone. Ancient Near Eastern Studies Presented to Krystyna Szarzynska on the Occasion of her 80th Birthday* (1998) 65-73; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 216-222; C.J. Crisostomo, *JANER* 15 (2015) 132-134; I. Peled, *AOAT* 435 (2016) 71-75; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 54-56; A. Cavigneaux, *RA* 114 (2020) 74-81; K. Boddy, *CM* 52 (2021) 97-109, 138-140, 171-174, index p. 459.

Nanše-Hymne (3.2.1.d): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 125-142; M. Jacques, *Nanše, déesse de Lagaš (mémoire de licence, Univ. de Genève, 1989) annexe II* (transcription et traduction); W. Heimpel, *The Context of Scripture I* 526-531; ETCSL 4.14.1 (1998); F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 102-116; Attinger, *TTS* (2012, actualisé en 2015); Attinger, *Mél. Charpin* (2019) 79-123 (édition). — Cf. S.N. Kramer, *Mél. Finet* 78-80; K. Lämmerhirt, *AOAT* 348 (2010) 492-496, 576, 625 sq. et 898 (index des passages traduits).

Ninmešarra (3.2.1.e): A. Zgoll, *AOAT* 246 (1997) (édition); W.W. Hallo, *The Context of Scripture I* 518-522; ETCSL 4.07.2 (1999); Betty De Shong Meador, *Inanna, Lady of Largest Heart: Poems of the Sumerian High Priestess Enheduanna* (2000) 168-191 et 206-208; Black et alii, *LAS* 315-320; Delnero, *Variation* 2021-2108 (partition); F. Lara Peinado,

Himnos sumerios (2006) 54-62; Attinger, TTS (2011, actualisé en 2015); Zgoll, Enheduana singt gegen die drohende Vernichtung. Ein sumerisches Lied für ein gefährliches Ritual, von der frühesten Autorin der Weltliteratur, dans: S. Franke (ed.), *Als die Götter Mensch waren* (2013) 77-87 et 119 sq.; ead., TUAT NF 8 (2015) 55-67; Zgoll, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 339-350 et 436; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 331-336.; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 93-98. — Cf. H. Sauren, JEOL 22 (1981/1982) 278-288; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 367-369; Zgoll. HANE/M III/2 (2000) 86-90.; S.G. Beld, *The Queen of Lagash: Ritual Economy in a Sumerian State* (Ph. D., University of Michigan 2002) 119-126; Zgoll, in: H. Felber (ed.) *Feinde und Aufrührer [...]* (2005) 294-300; Zgoll, in: R.G. Kratz/H. Spieckermann (ed.), *Götterbilder, Gottesbilder, Weltbilder. Polytheismus und Monotheismus in der Welt der Antike. Band I: Ägypten, Mesopotamien, Persien, Kleinasien, Syrien, Palästina* (Forschungen zum Alten Testament 2. Reihe Bd. 17, 2006) 115-124; A. Zgoll, in: J. Kügler/L. Bormann (ed.), *Töchter (Gottes). Studien zum Verhältnis von Kultur, Religion und Geschlecht. Bayreuther Forum 8* (2008) 7-21, surtout 13-20; J.-J. Glassner, *Topoi Suppl.* 10 (2009) 225-228; J. Keetman, *AoF* 37 (2010) 38-48; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 206-215; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= ORA 28, 2018) 109-111; S. Helle, *Autorship* 8 (2019) 12-15; B.R. Foster, dans K. Polinger Foster, *A Mesopotamian Miscellany* (2020) 20-24.

Nisaba-Hymne (3.2.1.f): Castellino, TSA 84 sqq.; ETCSL 4.1.6.1 (1999-2000).

Enlil/Nippur-Hymne (3.2.3.a): Castellino, TSA 45 sqq.; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 101-111; ETCSL 4.05.1 (1998); Black et alii, LAS 320-325; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 91-100; Delnero, *Variation 1217-1322 (études des variantes) et 2109-2172 (partition)*; F. Lara Peinado (2006) 8-18; Vanstiphout, *Eduba [...]* (2004) 91-100; Attinger, TTS (2014, actualisé en 2015); Attinger, CM 50 (2020) 54-120 (édition). — Cf. H. Sauren, JEOL 22 (1971/1972) 272-278; S.N. Kramer, *BiMes.* 4 (1976) 4 sq.; E.S. Gerstenberger, ORA 28 (2018) 166-171.

Eridu-Hymne (3.2.3.b): Cf. Enkis Reise nach Nippur (3.1.p 1).

Keš-Hymne (3.2.3.c): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 377-385; ETCSL 4.80.2 (1999); Black et alii, LAS 326-330; Delnero, *Variation 2173-2238 (partition)*; C. Wilcke, CM 35 (2006) 201-237.— Cf. M.J. Geller, ZA 86 (1996) 68-79; H. Steible, in: H.-J. Gehrke/A. Möller (ed.), *Vergangenheit und Lebenswelt [...]* (= *ScriptOralia* 90, 1996) 65-75.; M. Stol, CM 14 (2000) 76; P. Delnero, *The Textual Criticism of Sumerian Literature* (JCS Suppl. 3 [2012] 97-101; A. Zgoll, in: K. Schmid (ed.), *Schöpfung* (= *Themen der Theologie* 4, 2012) 27 sq.; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= ORA 28, 2018) 173-183; K. Maiwald, *Mesopotamische Schöpfungstexte in Ritualen [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 3, 2021) 211-225.

Nungal-Hymne (3.2.3.d): G.R. Castellino, *Orientalis Antiqui Collectio* 13, *Atti del 1° convegno italiano sul vicino Oriente antico* (Roma, 22-24 Aprile 1976), Rome, 1978, pp. 9-23; ETCSL 4.28.1 (1999); P. Attinger, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 15-34 (édition); Black et alii, LAS 339-342; Delnero, *Variation 2360-2395 (partition)*; Attinger, TTS (2011, actualisé en 2019). — Cf. B. Alster, RA 68 (1974) 60 n. 2; id., AOAT 25 (1976) 16 et n. 14; T.S. Frymer-

Kensky, *JESHO* 20 (1977) 78-89; Å.W. Sjöberg, *JCS* 29 (1977) 3-6 et 32-35; W.W. Hallo, *JCS* 31 (1979) 161-165 (= *WOL* 583-588); Frymer-Kensky, *RA* 79 (1985) 93 sq.; Alster/C.B.F. Walker, *Mél.* Sjöberg 7-10; M. Civil, *Mél.* Hallo 72-74; A. Annus, *NABU* 2010/85; K. Lämmerhirt, *AOAT* 348 (2010) 499-501, 577, 627 sq. et 899 (index des passages cités); C. Ambos, *Der König im Gefängnis und das Neujahrfest im Herbst [...] (2013)* 76 sq. et 81-83; Oshima, T., *Babylonian Poems of Pious Sufferers (ORA 14, 2014)* 311-313; A. Jordanova, *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015)* 374 sq.; A. Annus, *SAAS* 24 (2016) 61-64.

Tempelbauhymne des Gudea von Lagaš (3.2.3.e): Averbeck, *Ritual avec litt. ant.* (transcription et traduction pp. 589-712); Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 386-444; F. Lara Peinado, *Himno al Templo Eninnu. Cilindros A y B de Gudea (1996)*; E.J. Wilson, *AOAT* 244 (1996) (édition); D.O. Edzard, *RIME* 3/1 (1997) (édition); *ETCSL* 2.1.7 (1998); Averbeck, *The Context of Scripture II* 415-433 (traduction partielle); W.H.P. Römer, *AOAT* 376 (2010) (édition); S. Paulus, *TUAT NF* 7 (2013) 9-35 (cylindre A); W. Heimpel, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer (2015)* 119-165 et 420 sq. — Cf. C.E. Suter, *Gudea's Temple Building: A comparison of Written and Pictorial Accounts, Ph. D., Univ. of Pennsylvania 1995*; Averbeck in: G.D. Young/alii (eds.), *Crossing Boundaries and Linking Horizons. Studies in Honor of Michael C. Astour, Bethesda 1997*, 37-93; Suter, *ZA* 87 (1997) 1-10; B. Hruška, *AOAT* 267 (1999) 217-228; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 36-44; Suter, *Gudea's Temple Building: The Representation of an Early Mesopotamian Ruler in Text and Image (= CM 17, 2000)*; Suter, in: P. Azara et alii (ed.), *Mites de fundació de ciutats al món antic (Mesopotàmia, grècia i Roma): actes del col·loqui (Monografies 2, Barcelona 2001)* 81-90, surtout 84-89; J. Polonsky, *The Rise of the Sun God and the Determination of Destiny in Ancient Mesopotamia (PhD., Univ. of Philadelphia 2002)* 642-678 (index des passages cités pp. 1101f.); J.-J. Glassner, *Mél. H. et M. Tadmor (2003)* 62*-69*; G. Pettinato, *Il rituale della costruzione del tempio Eninnu nei cilindri di Gudea di Lagaš, dans: La casa del dio. Il tempio nella cultura del Vicino Oriente Antico. Atti del Convegno internazionale Milano, 31 gennaio 2004 (2005)* 31-52; Black et alii, *LAS* 44-52 (traduction partielle); B. Pongratz-Leisten, *BaM* 37 (2006) 45-59; A. Nagy, *NABU* 2007/35; A.R. Øiseth, *With roots in the Abzu and crown in the sky: Temple construction in between myth and reality – A study of the Eninnu temple of the Gudea cylinders as divine house and cosmic link. A dissertation presented to Institutt for Kulturstudier at the University of Oslo, for partial fulfilment of the degree of Master in History of Religion, 2007*; Averbeck, *AOAT* 366 (2010) 3-34 passim; S. Anthonioz, *Babel la tête dans le ciel, Suppl. n° 20 à Transeuphratène (2015)* 23-28; P. Steinkeller, dans: P. Steinkeller/M. Hudson (ed.), *Labor in the Ancient World (2015)* 146-153; C. Metcalf, dans: E.J. Hamori/J. Stökl (ed.), *Perchance to Dream: Dream Divination in the Bible and the Ancient Near East (2018)* 10-15; R.E. Averbeck, *AOAT* 460 (2020) 79-100; A. Zgoll, dans: B. Dieterle/M. Engel (ed.), *Historizing the Dream / Le rêve du point de vue historique, Cultural Dream Studies / Kulturwissenschaftliche Traum-Studien 3, Würzburg 2019*, 23-29; R.E. Averbeck, *AOAT* 460 (2020) 79-100.

Tempelliederzyklus (3.2.3.f): *ETCSL* 4.80.1 (1998-1999); Vanstiphout, *Eduba (2004)* 123-133; B.D.S. Meador, *Princess, Priestess, Poet: the Sumerian Temple Hymns of Enheduanna (2009)*; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors (2018)* 53-79. — Cf. Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki*

94 sq.; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/5 (1989) 686-688; J.A. Black, *NABU* 2002/4; F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 234-236; V.A. Hurowitz, *Mél. Abusch* (2010) 70-74; 77-79; V.K. Afanasieva, *BaBi*. 8 (2014) 1-9; A. Jordanova, *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten*. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015) 375 sq.; P. Espak, *Melammu* 2 (2019) 18 sq.; S. Helle, *Autorship* 8 (2019) 9-12; A. Johandi, *The God Asar/Asalluḫi in the Early Mesopotamian Pantheon* (*Dissertationes Theologiae Universitatis Tartuensis* 37, 2019) 81-88; J. Peterson, *JCS* 72 (2020) 129 sqq.

Preis der Hacke (3.2.4): G. Farber, *The Context of Scripture I* 511-513; *ETCSL* 5.5.4 (2000-2001); Black et alii, *LAS* 311-315; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 82-90; Delnero, *Variation* 2021-2108 (partition); G. Farber, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 69-76 et 418; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 46-50. — Cf. M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien* (*Supplément au Cahier Evangile* 64 [1988]) 22-24; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 508-511; G. Farber, *BBVO* 18 (1999) 369-373; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 416 sq.; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 16 (2004) 23 sq.; id., *MARG* 17 (2005) 139-141; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 28 sq.; P. Michalowski, *Mél. Owen* (2010) 195-200; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) sq.; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 55-57 et 296-304 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 57-59 et 324-329; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 183-187; K. Maiwald, *Mesopotamische Schöpfungstexte in Ritualen [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 3, 2021) 295-308.

Klagelied(er) (3.4.): Cf. W.W. Hallo, in: J.M. Sasson (ed.), *Civilizations of the Ancient Near East III* (1995) 1871-1881; A. Löhnert, *Motive und Funktionen der Göttinnenklagen im Frühen Mesopotamien*, *OBO* 251 (2011) 39-62; ead., *Manipulating the Gods: Lamenting in Context*, dans: K. Radner and E. Robson (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Cuneiform Culture* (2011) 402-417; N. Samet, *Encyclopedia of the Bible and Its Reception* 15 (2017) 687-691.

Historische Klage (3.4.1): Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *BBVO* 6 (1986) 1-11; P. Mander, *Mél. Moscati* (1996) I 261-269; B. Lion, *Âges d'or et paradis perdus dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: V. Pirenne-Delforge et Ö. Tunca (ed.), *Représentations du temps dans les religions*. Actes du Colloque organisé par le Centre d'Histoire des Religions de l'Université de Liège (2003) 68-72; J.S. Cooper, *JCS* 58 (2006) 39-47; G. Rubio, *Sumerian Literature*, in: C.S. Ehrlich (ed.), *From an Antique Land [...]* (2009) 62 sq.; D.L. Petter, *OBO* 246 (2011) 7-33 passim; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 276-279; N. Samet, *MC* 18 (2014) 1-13; U. Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts of the Gods [...]* (= *HES* 1, 2014) 13 sq.; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek, *De la steppe au bateau céleste ou comment Inanna accomplit son destin entre mythe et rite*, dans: N. Belayche/V. Pirenne-Delforge, *Fabriquer du divin. Constructions et ajustements de la représentation des dieux dans l'Antiquité* (2015) 29-34; J. Jacobs, *The city lament genre in the ancient Near East*, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), *The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy* (2016) 13-35.

Eridu-Klage (3.4.1.a): ETCSL 2.2.6 (1998). — Cf. Rollinger, *Frühformen* 217 sq.; I. Peled, *JCS* 67 (2015) 39-43; H. Schaudig, *dubsar* 13 (2019) 283 sq.

Nippur-Klage (3.4.1.b): S.N. Kramer, *ASJ* 13 (1991) 1-26 (édition); St. Tinney, *Nippur Lament: Royal Rhetoric and Divine Legitimation in the Reign of Isme-Dagan of Isin* (1953-1935 B.C.), *OPSNKF* 16,1996 (édition); ETCSL 2.2.4 (1998-1999); Attinger, *TTS* (2010, actualisé en 2015); J.L. Dahl/R.K. Englund, *CDLI* (2014-2015). — Cf. Rollinger, *Frühformen* 218-222; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *RIA* 9/7-8 (2001) 565 sq.; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 275-279; N. Samet, *MC* 18 (2014) 1-13 passim; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek, *De la steppe au bateau céleste ou comment Inanna accomplit son destin entre mythe et rite*, dans: N. Belayche/V. Pirenne-Delforge, *Fabriquer du divin. Constructions et ajustements de la représentation des dieux dans l'Antiquité* (2015) 29-33; H. Schaudig, *dubsar* 13 (2019) 284 sq.

Klage über Sumer und Ur (3.4.1.c): P. Michalowski, *The Lamentation over the Destruction of Sumer and Ur (= Mesopotamian Civilizations 1, Winona Lake, 1989) avec litt. ant.* (édition); ETCSL 2.2.3 (1998); Black et alii, *LAS* 127-141; Attinger, *TTS* (2009, actualisé en 2015); C.B. Hays, *Hidden Riches: A Sourcebook for the Comparative Study of the Hebrew Bible and Ancient Near East* (2014) 375-396 (traduction de P. Michalowski 1989, commentaire). — Cf. W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/5 (1989) 700-707; Rollinger, *Frühformen* 207-216; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 36; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 62 sq.; C. Wilcke, in: D. Hoffmann (ed.), *Vermächtnis der Abwesenheit. Spuren traumatisierender Ereignisse in der Kunst* (2000) 74-78 (traduction partielle); J. Kinnier-Wilson, *Iraq* 67 (2005) 49-56 passim; B. Studevent-Hickman, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *The Ancient Near East* (2006) 67-72; J.L. Dahl, *PIHANS* 108 (2011) 55-65 (v. à ce propos P. Attinger, *NABU* 2011/56); Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 273-277; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 96 sq.; N. Samet, *MC* 18 (2014) 1-13 passim; H. Schaudig, *dubsar* 13 (2019) 269-277.

Klage über die Zerstörung von Ur (3.4.1.d): M. Witzel, *Or.* 14 (1945) 185-234 et *Or.* 15 (1946) 46-63 (édition); Y. Rosengarten, *RHR* 174 (1968) 117-160; id., *Trois aspects de la pensée religieuse sumérienne* (Paris, 1971) 43-132; Castellino, *TSA* 283-301; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 447-474; ETCSL 2.2.2 (1998); W.H.P. Römer, *AOAT* 309 (2004) (édition); N. Samet, *The Lamentation over the Destruction of Ur. MC* 18, 2014 (édition); Attinger, *TTS* 2014; J.L. Dahl/R.K. Englund, *CDLI* (2014-2015). — Cf. J. Krecher, *ZA* 60 (1970) 202 sq.; H. Sauren, *JNES* 29 (1970) 42-47; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 301 sq.; Rollinger, *Frühformen* 216 sq.; J. Klein, *The Context of Scripture I* 535-539 (traduction partielle); C. Wilcke, in: D. Hoffmann (ed.), *Vermächtnis der Abwesenheit. Spuren traumatisierender Ereignisse in der Kunst* (2000) 71-74 (traduction partielle); D.E. Fleming, *The Classical World* 97 (2003) 5-18 passim; J. Kinnier-Wilson, *Iraq* 67 (2005) 51-58 passim; N. Samet, *NABU* 2010/62 (joins et nouvelles lectures); P. Attinger, *NABU* 2011/57; A. Löhnert, *JCS* 63 (2011) 65-72 (édition d'un nouveau duplicat); N. Samet and S.F. Adalı, *JCS* 64 (2012) 31-37 (nouveaux duplicats, traduction partielle); P. Attinger, *Or.* 84 (2015) 41-74 ("review-article" de Samet 2014); J. Jacobs, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), *The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy* (2016) 25-30; L. Vacín, *ArOr.* 85 (2017) 461-478 ("review-article" de Samet 2014); H. Schaudig,

dubsar 13 (2019) 279-283; B.R. Foster, dans K. Polinger Foster, *A Mesopotamian Miscellany* (2020) 57-59.

Uruk-Klage (3.4.1.e): ETCSL 2.2.5 (1998). A. Cavigneaux, *ZA* 103 (2013) 4-15. — Cf. Rollinger, *Frühformen* 222-226; J. Polonsky, *The Rise of the Sun God and the Determination of Destiny in Ancient Mesopotamia* (PhD., Univ. of Philadelphia 2002) 704-709, N. Samet, *MC* 18 (2014) 1-13 passim; H. Schaudig, *dubsar* 13 (2019) 278 sq.

Klage über die Zerstörung der Heiligtümer von Lagaš (3.4.1.f): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* I/4 (1984) 313-315; J.S. Cooper, *Sumerian and Akkadian Royal Inscriptions, I: Presargonic Inscriptions* (New Haven 1986) 78-79. D.R. Frayne, *RIME* 1 (2008) 276-279 (édition). — Cf. F. Pomponio, *Formule di maledizione della Mesopotamia preclassica* (Brescia 1990) 20; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (Milano 1991) 234-235; J. Krecher, *Gs. Kutscher* (1993) 114-117 (i 6-9 //); M.A. Powell, *WZKM* 86 (1996) 307-314; G. Cunningham, *StPohl SM* 17 (1997) 47-48 (vii 10-ix 3); J. Bauer, *OBO* 160/1 (1998) 489-493.

Persönliche Klage (3.4.4): Cf. M. Jaques, *Metaphern als Kommunikationsstrategie in den mesopotamischen Bußgebeten an den persönlichen Gott*, *OBO* 251 (2011) 3-19; ead., *OBO* 273 (2015).

Der Mensch und sein Gott (3.4.4): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/1 (1990) 102-109; ETCSL 5.2.4 (1998-1999); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 270-277. — Cf. J. van Dijk, *SSA* 122-127; id. dans J.P. Asmussen/*alii* (ed.), *Handbuch der Religionsgeschichte I* (Göttingen, 1971) 493-496; S.N. Kramer, *BiMes.* 4 (1976) 10 sq.; J. Klein, *AfO Bh.* 19 (1982) 297-306; G.L. Mattingly dans W.W. Hallo, B.W. Jones and G.L. Mattingly (ed.), *The Bible in the Light of Cuneiform Literature: Scripture In Context III* (= *Ancient Near Eastern Texts and Studies* 8, 1990) 305-348; D. Sitzler, *Vorwurf gegen Gott* (= *Studies in Oriental Religions* 32, 1995) 61-71; Klein, *The Context of Scripture I* 573-575 (traduction partielle); H. Limet, *Transeuphratène* 22 (2001) 117 sq.; O. Loretz, *AOAT* 290 (2003) 188-190; Klein, *CM* 35 (2006) 123-143; C. Uehlinger, dans: T. Krüger et al. (ed.), *Das Buch Hiob und seine Interpretationen. Beiträge zum Hiob-Symposium auf dem Monte Verità vom 14.-19. August 2005* (2007) 128-132; S. Fink, *Kaskal* 9 (2012) 77 sq.; T. Oshima, *ORA* 14 (2014) 19-22; M. Jaques, *OBO* 273 (2015) 4-10; N. Ziegler, *OBO* 278 (2015) 219 sq.

Briefe an Götter (3.5.1): ETCSL 3.3/... (2001). — Cf. B. Böck, *AoF* 23 (1996) 3-23; B. Pongratz-Leisten, *SAAS* 10 (1999) 213-217; D. Bodi, *Ktéma* 33 (2008) 246-249; A. Kleinerman, *CM* 42 (2011) 35-37; A. Löhnert, *WO* 44 (2014) 203-208.

Königsbriefe (3.5.2): ETCSL 3.1/... et 3.2/... (2001). A. Kleinerman, *Education in Early 2nd Millennium BC Babylonia*. *CM* 42, 2011; P. Michalowski, *The Correspondence of the Kings of Ur*. *MC* 15, 2011; Attinger, *TTS* (ANL 7, 9 [2013-2014]; CKU 1, 2, 4, 8, 18, 21, 23, 24 [2012]; SEpM 2, 4-7, 16-19 [2013]). — Cf. F. Huber, *ZA* 91 (2001) 169-206; P. Michalowski, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 262-267; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 58-68; W.W. Hallo, *CM* 35 (2006) 85-104 (= *WOL* 385-405); P. Michalowski, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *The Ancient Near East* (2006) 75-81; A. Kleinerman, *Kaskal* 5 (2008) 173-186; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.), *The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600* (2011) 18-20; F. Huber Vulliet, dans: K. Radner and E. Robson (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Cuneiform Culture* (2011) 486-507, surtout 489 sqq.

(*Epische*) *Streitgespräche* (3.6.1.): Cf. en général B. Alster dans E. Keck/*alii* (ed.), *Living Waters ... Presented to F. Løkkegaard* (Copenhagen, 1990) 1-16 avec litt. ant.; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *ASJ* 12 (1990) 271-318 avec litt. ant.; id., *OLA* 42 (1991) 23-46; id., *ASJ* 14 (1992) 339-367; ID, *Res Orientales IV* (1992) 12-21; S. Ponchia, *La palma e il tamarisco e altri dialoghi mesopotamici* (Venise 1996); Alster, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 288-291; D.O. Edzard, *OBO* 160/4 (2004) 524 sq.; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 153-203; S. Herrmann, *Saeculum* 59 (2008) 201-212; ead., *Vogel und Fisch*; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 13-26. — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar (2010) 17-95; M. Lang, *Sieg und Nicht-Sieg in altorientalischen Streitgedichten*, dans: M. Fahlenbock / L. Madersbacher / I. Schneider (ed.), *Inszenierung des Sieges — Sieg der Inszenierung. Interdisziplinäre Perspektiven* (Innsbruck 2011) 69-77; K. Volk, *RIA* 13/3-4 (2012) 214-222 s.v. *Streitgespräch*; H. Vanstiphout, *CM* 46 (2014) 229-240; F. Kilchör/C. Mittermayer, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 225-240; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 447-457; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) passim; ead., *SANER* 25 (2020) 11-32.

Edelmetall und Kupfer (3.6.1.a): *ETCSL* 5.3.6 (2000); *DSSSt* Q000765 (état 2020, sans traduction). — Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *OLA* 42 (1991) 26 n. 17 (bibl.); Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 23 sq./47; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 23; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 449.

Enmerkar und En-MÛŠ-kéšda-anna (3.6.1.b): *ETCSL* 1.8.2.4 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 68-83; Black et alii, *LAS* 3-11; Vanstiphout, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta (= Writings from the Ancient World 20, 2004)* 23-48; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuhgiranna* (2006), surtout 66-126; Attinger, *TTS* (2008, actualisé en 2015); C. Wilcke, *The Sumerian Poem Enmerkar and En-suhkeš-ana: Epic, Play, Or? [...]. AOS Essay* 12, 2012; C. Mittermayer/P. Attinger, *Enmerkara und Ensukukešdana, dubsar* 17 (2020) 191-262; *DSSSt* Q000370 (état 2020). — Cf. W. Heimpel, *JAOS* 101 (1981) 404-407; H. Behrens, *AfO* 29-30 (1983/1984) 98-103; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 151-153; Attinger, *Eléments* 36 (reconstruction du texte); Vanstiphout, *OLP* 26 (1995) 5-20; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 212 sq.; G. Zólyomi, *NABU* 2003/61 (reconstruction du texte); D. Schwemer, *Abwehrzauber und Behexung. Studien zum Schadenzauberglauben im alten Mesopotamien* (2008) 135-137; Vanstiphout, *Gs. Black* 361-377 passim; C. Mittermayer, *ORA* 10 (2013) 32-34; F. Hazelton, *Three Kings of Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia* (2013) 1-10 (renarration); Peterson, *NABU* 2015/64; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 58 (2017) 376-378 (à propos des ll. 171-183, 197-199); L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 448 sq.; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 107-110 (à propos des ll. 224-271); C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 11.

Hacke und Pflug (3.6.1.c): H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 578-581; *ETCSL* 5.3.1 (2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 156-167; D.O. Edzard, *OBO* 160/4 (2004) 525-531 (translit. et traduction partielles); Attinger, *TTS* (2010, actualisé en 2019); C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 1-36 passim, 109-137, 139-161 passim, 285-354 (édition); *DSSSt* Q0007600 (état 2020). — Cf. Hruška, *Ackerbau* 495-499; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 45-47; 76 sq.; 91 sq.; 93 sq.; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 17; R. Pientka-Hinz, dans: J. Renn et al.

(ed.), *Wissensgeschichte der Architektur Band I: vom Neolithikum bis zum Alten Orient* (2017) 297-299; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 447 sq. avec n. 10, 452.

Holz und Rohr (3.6.1.d): Cf. J. van Dijk, *ActOr.* 28 (1964) 44-57; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 479-481; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 357-360; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 100 sq.; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 19 sq./46; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 43 et 70-95 passim; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 38 sq. et 229-233 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 39 sq. et 251-255; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 20 sq.; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 452-455.

Mutterschaf und Getreide (3.6.1.e): B. Alster/H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *ASJ* 9 (1987) 1-43 avec litt. ant. (édition); Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 575-578 (traduction partielle); Black et alii, *LAS* 225-229; *ETCSL* 5.3.2 (1999-2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 186-194; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 1-36 passim, 37-66, 139-161 passim, 163-227 (édition); *DSSSt* Q000761 (état 2020). — Cf. J. Bauer, *AfO* Bh. 19 (1982) 377-383; M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988])* 40 sq.; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 511-514; Hruška, *Ackerbau* 499-505; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 325 sq. et 378 sq.; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *Res Orientales* IV (1992) 18-21; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 67 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 427-429; M. Tanret, *Mél. Klener* (2004) 186-191; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 22 sq.; J. Marzahn, dans: J. Marzahn und G. Schauerte (ed.), *Babylon: Wahrheit* (2008) 234 sq.; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 70-95 passim; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 20 (2010) 40-44; A. Schellenberg, *Der Mensch, das Bild Gottes? Zum Gedanken einer Sonderstellung des Menschen im Alten Testament und in witeren altorientalischen Quellen* *ATHANT* 101, (2011) 261-269; A. Zgoll, in: K. Schmid (ed.), *Schöpfung (= Themen der Theologie* 4, (2012) 60-62; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 88-90; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 39-42 et 234-257 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 40-44 et 256-281; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 17-19; F. Kilchör/C. Mittermayer, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 225-240 passim; ead., *SANER* 25 (2020) 16-26, 28.

Reiher und Schildkröte (3.6.1.f): T.J.H. Krispijn, dans: W.L. Idema et al. (ed.), *"Mijn naam is haas." Dierenverhalten in verschillende culturen* (1993) 144-148 (traduction partielle); G.B. Gragg, *The Context of Scripture I* 571-573 (traduction partielle); *ETCSL* 5.9.2 (1999-2000); Black et alii, *LAS* 235-240; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 179-186; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* (2007) 269-410 (édition partielle). — Cf. S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 53 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 11.

Sommer und Winter (3.6.1.g): H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 584-588; *ETCSL* 5.3.3 (1999-2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 167-179. — Cf. Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 481-483; Vanstiphout, *ASJ* 14 (1992) 339 sqq., surtout 348-352/363-366; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* 468-487 (ll. 69-79); Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 18 sq./44 sq.; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 41 sq. et 70-95 passim; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 19 sq.; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 450-452.

Vogel und Fisch (3.6.1.h): ETCSL 5.3.5 (1999-2000); Black et alii, LAS 230-235; Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 194-203; S. Herrmann, Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar (2010); C. Mittermayer, UAVA 15 (2019) 1-36 passim, 67-97, 139-161 passim, 228-284 (édition); DSSSt Q000764 (état 2020). — S.N. Kramer, CRRAI 11 (1962, ed. 1964) 96-101; id., Phoenix 10 (1964) 102-108; T.J.H. Krispijn, dans: W.L. Idema et al. (ed.), "Mijn naam is haas." Dierenverhalten in verschillende culturen (1993) 138-144; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, The Context of Scripture I 581-584; C. Mittermayer, mušen ku₆: Viel Vogel und wenig Fisch in MS 2110/1, AoF 41 (2014) 201-222 (édition partielle). — Cf. Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 517-519; Kramer/Maier, Myths of Enki 86 sq.; G. Pettinato, Mitologia sumerica (2001) 115 sq.; Wilcke, Anfänge (2007) 20 sq.; J. C. Johnson, AoF 37 (2010) 230-241; E. Jiménez, CHANE 87 (2017) 21 sq.; F. Kilchör/C. Mittermayer, CRRAI 61 (2018) 225-240 passim; ead. in R. Mattila et al. (ed.), Animals and their Relation to Gods, Humans and Things in the Ancient World (2019) 175-186.

Hirte und Bauer (3.6.1.i): SRT 3 // (Dumuzi et Enkimdu) n'est pas la suite de BE 30 4 (= PBS 1/1 6) // (Dumuzi-Inanna A).

a) Dumuzi-Inanna A²: Sefati, Love Songs 120-127 avec litt. ant. (édition); Jacobsen, The Harps that once ... 13-15; ETCSL 4.08.01 (1998); Black et alii, LAS 206-209; P. Mander, Canti sumerici d'amore e morte (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005) 106-109; Attinger, TTS (2010, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. Kramer/Molina, El Matrimonio Sagrado 81-83 et 182 sq.; M.M. Fritz, AOAT 307 (2003) 82; P. Lapinkivi, SAAS 15 (2004) 31 sq.; M.E. Couto-Ferreira, SANER 12 (2017) 62 sq.

b) Dumuzi et Enkimdu: Sefati, Love Songs 324-343 avec litt. ant. (édition); ETCSL 4.08.33 (1999); Black et alii, LAS 86-88; P. Mander, Canti sumerici d'amore e morte (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005) 114-118; Attinger, TTS (2010, actualisé en 2015); DSSSt Q000663 (état 2020). — Cf. P. Attinger, NABU 1996/110; Kramer/Molina, El Matrimonio Sagrado 70 et 84-86 et 183; M.M. Fritz, AOAT 307 (2003) 88; C. Mittermayer, BaBi. 8 (2014) 383-397; ead., UAVA 15 (2019) 10 sq.

Schulstreitgespräche (3.6.2): Cf. en général K. Volk, Saeculum 47 (1996) 178-216; ZA 90 (2000) 1-30; B. Alster, Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible 73 (2002) 291-293; Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 219 sqq.; K. Volk, RIA 13/3-4 (2012) 220-222; C. Mittermayer, UAVA 15 (2019) 3-7; M. Ceccarelli, SANER 25 (2020) 33-55.

Streit zweier Schulabsolventen ("Dialogue 1") (3.6.2.a): J. Cale Johnson and M.J. Geller, CM 47 (2015) (édition); J. Matuszak, ZA 109 (2019) 1-47 (nouveaux duplicats, texte reconstruit, traduction, commentaire); DSSSt Q000767 (état 2020). — Cf. M. Ceccarelli, SANER 25 (2020) 37 sq.

Enkitalu und Enki-hegal ("Dialogue 2") (3.6.2.b). DSSSt Q000768 (état 2020, sans traduction). — Cf. M. Ceccarelli, AoF 45 (2018) 133-155 passim; id., SANER 25 (2020) 36 sq., 42-44, 49 sq.

Enki-mansum und Girine-isa ("Dialogue 3") (3.6.2.c): DSSSt Q000769 (état 2020, sans traduction). — Cf. W.H.Ph. Römer, UF 20 (1988) 233-245 avec litt. ant. (édition

² L'incipit est ʿses¹-e nin₉-ra.

partielle); id., TUAT III/1 (1990) 91-98; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 589-590 (traduction partielle); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 219-224. — Cf. M. Ceccarelli, *AoF* 45 (2018) 133-155 passim; id., *SANER* 25 (2020) 37, 44-47.

Der Schreiber und sein 'Aufseher' ("Dialogue 4") (3.6.2.d): H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* (1997) 590-592 (traduction partielle); *ETCSL* 5.1.3 (2000); C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 23-30 (traduction partielle); Black et al., *LAS* 277-280; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 224-229; N. Koslova, *BaBi*. 8 (2014) 317-324 (translit. et traduction partielles); K. Volk, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 109-116 et 420; *DSSSt Q000756* (état 2020, sans traduction).

"Edubbâ Regulations" (3.6.2.e): Cf. M. Civil, *Mél. Birot* 73 n.4.

Streit zweier Frauen ("Dialogue 5") (3.6.2.f) J. Matuszak, "Und du, du bist eine Frau?!" *Editio princeps* und Analyse des sumerischen Streitgesprächs 'Zwei Frauen B', *UAVA* 16 (2021) (édition). — Cf. K. Volk, *ZA* 90 (2000) 16-20; J. Matuszak, *SANER* 25 (2020) 57-74.

Schulsatiren (3.6.3): Cf. en général K. Volk, *Saeculum* 47 (1996) 178-216; B. Alster, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 291-293; C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 10-31; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 205-219, 235-244.

Der Sohn des 'Tafelhauses' (3.6.3.a): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 68-77; D.O. Edzard, *OBO* 160/4 (2004) 531-539 (édition); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 206-211; Attinger, *TTS* (2009, actualisé en 2015); K.S. Schmidt, *Aus dem Leben eines Schülers*, dans: S. Franke (ed.), *Als die Götter Mensch waren* (2013) 110-114 et 122; R.K. Englund, *CDLI P464238* (2014); K. Volk, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 101-107 et 420; *DSSSt Q000754* (état 2020). — Cf. C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 17-19; Peterson, J., *AulOr.* 33 (2015) 93 sq.

Der Vater und sein mißratener Sohn (3.6.3.b): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 77-91; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 211-219. — Cf. B. Alster, *RA* 69 (1975) 81-84; C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 19-23.

Examenstext A (3.7.1.a): Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 238-243. — Cf. J.A. Black, *StPohl SM* 12 (1984) 72-74.

Examenstext D (3.7.1.b): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 46-48; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 243 sq. — Cf. G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 350; V.A. Hurowitz, *JANES* 27 (2000) 49-56.

Unterweisungen eines Bauern an seinen Sohn (3.7.1.c): M. Civil, *The Farmer's Instructions* [...] (= *AulOr. Suppl.* 5, 1994); *ETCSL* 5.6.3 (1999); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 117-123; S. Paulus, *TUAT NF* 9 (2020) 141-151. — Cf. Th. Jacobsen, *BiMes.* 14 (1982) 56-60; Hruška, *Ackerbau* 491-495; A. Cavigneaux, *AulOr.* 9 (1991) 37-46; Hruška, *ZDMG Suppl.* 10 (1994) 23-31; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 136-141.

Unterweisungen des Šuruppag an seinen Sohn Ziusudra (3.7.1.d): W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT III/1 (1990) 48-67; ETCSL 5.6.1 (1999); Black et alii, LAS 284-292; B. Alster, *Wisdom of Ancient Sumer* (2005) 31-220 und pl. 1-15, 17-29 und 60-69 (édition). — Cf. B. Alster, *AulOr.* 5 (1987) 199-206; M. Civil, *ib.* 207-210; Alster, *ZA* 80 (1990) 15-19; id., dans: A. Assmann (ed.), *Weisheit [...]* (München, 1991) 103-115, surtout 103-109; J.R. Davila, *JNES* 54 (1995) 202; Alster, *The Context of Scripture I* 569-570 (traduction partielle); Alster, dans: K. Eksell/L. Feldt (ed.), *Readings in Eastern Mediterranean Literatures* (2006) 46-49 (traduction partielle); Gadotti, *Sumerian wisdom literature* 62-64, 70 sq.; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 8 sq., 101-103, 132-139; J. Fechner, *Moral Concepts within the Sumero-Akkadian Proverbial Literature: Origins, Developments and Tendencies*, dans: M-S. Ortola/G. Achard-Bayle (ed.), *Cocepts éthiques et moraux: approches multiculturelles et interdisciplinaires. Sémantique des énoncés parémiques* (2015) 21-25; J. Klein/N. Samet, *Mém. Hurowitz* (2015) 299-303; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 210-212/224 sq.; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 57 sq.; W. Sallaberger, dans M. Cogan (ed.), *In the Lands of Sumer and Akkad: New Studies. A Conference in Honor of JACOB KLEIN on the Occasion of His Eightieth Birthday* (2018) vii-xxviii.

Sumerische Königsliste (3.7.2.a): W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT I/4 (1984) 328-337; J.-J. Glassner, *Chroniques mésopotamiennes* (Paris, 1993) 137-142 (discussion pp. 69-87; 113-117); ETCSL 2.1.1 (1999); P. Steinkeller, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 267-292 (éd. d'une version d'Ur III); Glassner, *Mesopotamian Chronicles* (2005) 117-127 (discussion pp. 55-70 et 95-99); P. Michalowski, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *The Ancient Near East* (2006) 81-85; J. Kaula, *CDLP* 5 (2016) (édition de WB 1923.444); G. Gabriel, TUAT NF 9 (2020) 54-62 (traduction de la version d'Ur III). — Cf. A. Westenholz, *JCS* 26 (1974) 154-156; B. Lukács/L. Végso, *AoF* 2 (1975) 25-45; R.R. Wilson, *YNER* 7 (1977) 72-86; A. Kammenhuber, *Or.* 48 (1979) 1-25; M.J. Geller, *Eblaitica* 1 (1987) 141-145; C. Wilcke *apud* Hrouda, *Isin III* 89-93; M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988])* 45-47; G. Steiner, *ASJ* 10 (1988) 129-152; Wilcke dans J. von Ungern-Sternberg/H. Reinau, *Colloquium Rauricum, Band 1, Vergangenheit in mündlicher Überlieferung* (Stuttgart, 1988) 113-140; D.W. Young, *JNES* 47 (1988) 123-129; Wilcke, *Mél. Sjöberg* 557-571; C. Vincente, *NABU* 1990/11; J. Klein, *AulOr.* 9 (1991) 123-129; W. Heimpel, *ZA* 82 (1992) 9 sq.; Steiner, *CRAI* 35 (1988, ed. 1992) 261-279; J.S. Cooper, *HANES* 5 (1993) 19 sq.; Rollinger, *Frühformen* 227-235; J.R. Davila, *JNES* 54 (1995) 201; Vincente, *ZA* 85 (1995) 234-270; Glassner, *Les temps de l'histoire en Mésopotamie*, dans: A. de Pury et al. (rd.), *Israël construit son histoire* (1996) 167-189 (SKL: 170-175); J.S. Cooper, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 72 (1999) 243-245; E. Flückiger-Hawker, *OBO* 166 (1999) 41 sq.; Wilcke dans D. Kuhn/H. Stahl (ed.), *Die Gegenwart des Altertums* (2001) 101-116; G.J. Selz, *Die Königsliste als politische Tendenzwerke*, in: M. Heinz und D. Bonatz (ed.), *Der "Garten Eden" im dritten Jahrtausend [...]* (= *Freiburger Universitätsblätter Heft 156, Juni 2002, 41. Jahrgang*) 21-30; A. Westenholz, dans M.H. Hansen (ed.), *A Comparative Study of Six City-State Cultures* (2002) 32 sq.; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT* 307 (2003) 165 sq.; Glassner, dans: N. Grimal et M. Béaud (ed.), *Événement, récit, histoire officielle. L'écriture de l'histoire dans les monarchies antiques* (2003) 70-81; G. Pettinato, *I re di Sumer I* (2003) 49-60; D.O. Edzard, *Geschichte Mesopotamiens* (2004) 38-41; Glassner, *Mél. Klein* (2004) 138-141; M. Haul, *CDOG* 3 (2004) 240-242 et 245-250; N. Veldhuis, *CM* 22 (2004) 76 sq.; H.D. Galter, *AOAT* 325 (2005) 276-285; Glassner, *NABU*

2005/46; J. Friberg, *MSCCT* 1 (2007) 231-243; J. Klein, *Mél. Sigrist* (2008) 77-91; P. Panitschek, *LUGAL — šarru — basileús [...]* (2008) 457-465; J. Peterson, *AulOr.* 26 (2008) 257-262, surtout 257 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *OBO* 239 (2009) 90-95; D. Frayne, *CSMS Journal* 4 (2009) 39-41; J. Cooper, *JAOS* 130 (2010) 330-333; Klein, *CRRAI* 53/1 (2010) 1127 sqq.; G. Marchesi, *Mél. Mayer* (2010) 231-248; J.M. Sasson, *Mél. Foster* (2010) 361-373; A.R. George, *CUSAS* 17 (2011) 199-205/pl. LXXVIII-LXXXIV n° 96-99 (nouveaux duplicats); G. Marchesi, *MC* 14 (2011) 114-118; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.), *The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600* (2011) 15 sq.; L. Vacin, *Šulgi of Ur: Life, Deeds, Ideology and Legacy of a Mesopotamian Ruler as Reflected primarily in Literary Texts* (PhD, University of London 2011) 221-227; Y. Cohen, *Iraq* 74 (2012) 140 sqq.; 6-8, 76 sq., 103 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *CRRAI* 54 (2012) 313-326; P. Charvát, *CRRAI* 57 (2015) 75-80; W. Sallaberger/I. Schrakamp, *Arcane* 3 (2015) 13-22; S.J. Milstein, *Tracking the Master Scribe: Revision through Introduction in Biblical and Mesopotamian Literature* (2016) 45-50; W. Sommerfeld, *Arcane* 3 (2015) 271 sq.; T. Janssen, *NABU* 2016/35; M.R. Bachvarova, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), *The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy* (2016) 39 sq.; N. Brisch *Mél. Postgate* (2017) 322-330 passim; P. Steinkeller, *SANER* 15 (2017) 40-42, 44 sq., 58-61, 72-78, 180-183, 192-196, index p. 226; G. Gabriel, *AVO* 19 (2018) 71-131; P. Michalowski, dans: J. Baines et al. (ed.), *Historical Consciousness and the Use of the Past in the Ancient World* (2019) 16-24, 30-33; C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 199-204.

(Parodistische?) Königsliste von Lagaš (3.7.2.b): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 520-525; J.-J. Glassner, *Chroniques mésopotamiennes* (Paris, 1993) 151-153; *ETCSL* 2.1.2 (1998-1999); Glassner, *Mesopotamian Chronicles* (2005) 144-149. — Cf. M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien* (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988]) 41 sq.; B.F. Batto, dans: K.L. Younger et alii (ed.), *The Biblical Canon in Comparative Perspective. Scripture in Context IV* (1991) 46-48; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 189 sq.; Kobayashi, *Bulletin of the Orient Museum* 10 () 125-151 (cf. Sigrist/alii, *CBTBM* II 254); J.S. Cooper, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 72 (1999) 245; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 422-424; id., *I re di Sumer I* (2003) 62-64; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 20 (2010) 47-50; B.F. Batto, *In the Beginning: Essays on Creation Motifs in the Ancient Near East and the Bible* (2013) 71 sq.; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 104-106; P. Steinkeller, *SANER* 15 (2017) 42 sq.

Tummal-'Chronik' (3.7.2.c): *SumLet. B:* 9 (édition); J.-J. Glassner, *Chroniques mésopotamiennes* (Paris, 1993) 155 sq.; *ETCSL* 2.1.3 (1998); J. Oelsner, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 209-224 (édition); G. Pettinato, *I re di Sumer I* (2003) 60-62; Glassner, *Mesopotamian Chronicles* (2005) 156-159; P. Michalowski, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *The Ancient Near East* (2006) 85-87; A. Kleinerman, *CM* 42 (2011) 141-143 et 243-253 (éd.). — Cf. J.S. Cooper, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 72 (1999) 245 sq.; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 104-106; P. Michalowski, *CM* 35 (2006) 145-165; M. Hilgert, *RIA* 14 (2014-2016) 183 sq.; P. Steinkeller, dans: P. Steinkeller et al. (ed.), *Labor in the Ancient World* (2015) 157 sq., 162 sq. et 211; T. Sharlach, *Mél. Sigrist* (2020) 440 sqq.

Utu-ḫegal-Epos (3.7.2.d): E. Sollberger/J.-R. Kupper, *LAPPO* 3 (1971) 130-132; D.R. Frayne, *RIME* 2 (1993) 283-293 (édition); *ETCSL* 2.1.6 (1998); W. Sallaberger, *König Utuhengal vertreibt die Gutäer*, dans: S. Franke (ed.), *Als die Götter Mensch waren* (2013)

88-90 et 120. — Cf. G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 276 sq.; Rollinger, *Frühformen* 33-36; M. Widell, *JAC* 15 (2000) 59-65; P. Espak, *AOAT* 390/4 (2016) 80-86; F. D'Agostino et al., *La lingua dei Sumeri* (2019) 207-208.

Rätsel (3.7.3.b): M. Civil, *AulOr.* 5 (1987) 17-37. — Cf. Civil, *NABU* 1988/43; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/1 (1990) 44-46; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 52-56; A. Cavigneaux, *RIA* 11/3-4 (2007) 224.

Sammlungen von 'Sprichwörtern' (3.7.3.c): B. Alster, *Assyriological Miscellanies* 1 (1980) 33-50 (édition de SP 24); R.S. Falkowitz, *The Sumerian Rhetoric Collections*. Ph. D., Univ. of Pennsylvania, 1980 (édition de SP 3); B. Alster, *Proverbs of Ancient Sumer*. Bethesda, 1997 (édition de toutes les collections); J. Black et al., *ETCSL* 6.1-6.2 (2002); B. Alster, *Wisdom of Ancient Sumer* (2005) 391-403 (chapitre 6: Examples of Proverb Collections Used as Literary Source Books); B. Alster, *Sumerian Proverbs in the Schøyen Collection* (= *CUSAS* 2, 2007) (édition). — Cf. aussi S.N. Kramer, *CRRAI* 3 (1954) 75-84; M. Lambert, *RSO* 42 (1967) 75-99 et *RSO* 45 (1970) 29-58; G.D. Young, *JCS* 24 (1971-1972) 132; Kramer, *OECT* 5 (1976) 36-41 (Proverbs); J. Bauer, *AoN* 15 dans *AoN* 9-17 (1980); W.W. Hallo, *JQR* 76 (1985) 21-40 (= *WOL* 589-605); id., *Mél. Moran* 203-217 (= *WOL* 607-623); W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/1 (1990) 31-43; B. Alster, *NABU* 1992/82; id., *Proverbium* 10 (1993) 1-20; Bauer, *Mél. Hallo* 39 sq.; T.J.H. Krispijn, dans: W.L. Idema et al. (ed.), "Mijn naam is haas." *Dierenverhalten in verschillende culturen* (1993) 132-136; Alster, *CM* 6 (1996) 1-21; A. Cavigneaux, *Mél. Limet* (1996) 19-21 (CBS 11945); N. Veldhuis, *JAOS* 120 (2000) 383-399; Alster, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 293-299; Black, J. et alii, *LAS* (2004) 282 sq.; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 47-52; J. Taylor, *RA* 99 (2005) 13-38; Alster/T. Oshima, *Or.* 75 (2006) 31-72; Alster, *Or.* 75, 380-389; A. Cavigneaux, *Textes lexicaux et littéraires*, dans C. Proust, *Tablettes mathématiques de Nippur* (2007) 325-356 passim; L. Muntingh, *JSem.* 16 (2007) 708-714; Taylor, dans: J. Ebeling and G. Cunningham (ed.) *Analysing Literary Sumerian: Corpus-based Approaches* (London-Oakville: Equinox Publishing Ltd 2007) 273-315; M. Krebernik, *TMH* 8 (2008) 79-82; S. Seminara, *Or.* 78 (2009) 379-393; E. Frahm, *Mél. Foster* (2010) 155-184; G.J. Selz, dans: P. Charvát and P.M. Vlcková (ed.), *Who Was King? Who Was Not King [...]* (2010) 8-13; S. Seminara, *Mél. Mayer* (2010) 369-374; B. Alster, *PIHANS* 118 (2011) 9-27; J. Peterson, *BPOA* 9 (2011) 243-299; N. Wasserman, *RIA* 13/1-2 (2011) 19-23 passim; A. Cavigneaux, *OBO* 256 (2012) 84 sq.; A. Gadotti, dans M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *Women in the Ancient Near East* (2014) 60-62 et 68-70; J. Klein, *BaBi* 8. (2014) 271-304; J. Fechner, *Moral Concepts within the Sumero-Akkadian Proverbial Literature: Origins, Developments and Tendencies*, dans: M-S. Ortola/G. Achard-Bayle (ed.), *Cocepts éthiques et moraux: approches multiculturelles et interdisciplinaires. Sémantique des énoncés parémiqes* (2015) 17-60, surtout 30-42; J. Klein/N. Samet, *Mél. Hurowitz* (2015) 295-321; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 63-65 et 103 sq.; G. Konstantopoulos, *Kaskal* 14 (2017) 125-140; P. Attinger, *AoF* 46 (2019) 161-173; C.J. Crisostomo, *SANER* 22 (2019) 70-73; id., *Kaskal* 16 (2019) 141-157.

Early Dynastic Proverb Coll. 1: Alster, *AfO* 38-39 (1991/1992) 1-51 (édition). — Cf. aussi J. Klein, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 135-149; J. Fechner, *Moral Concepts within the Sumero-Akkadian Proverbial Literature: Origins, Developments and Tendencies*, dans: M-S.

Ortola/G. Achard-Bayle (ed.), *Concepts éthiques et moraux: approches multiculturelles et interdisciplinaires. Sémantique des énoncés parémiques* (2015) 24-28.

Beschwörungen (3.8.1): M. Krebernik, *Die Beschwörungen aus Fara und Ebla. Untersuchungen zur ältesten keilschriftlichen Beschwörungsliteratur* (= TSO 2, 1984); P. Michalowski, *QdS* 18 (1992) 305-326; G. Cunningham, 'Deliver me from Evil' [...], *StPohl SM* 17, Roma 1997; *Magic in the Ancient Near East*, SEL 15 (1998); T. Abush/K. van der Toorn (ed.), *Mesopotamian Magic* [...] (= AMD 1, 1999); M.J. Geller, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 269-283; J.J.A van Dijk/M.J. Geller, *TMH* 6 (2003); N. Rudik, *Die Entwicklung der keilschriftlichen sumerischen Beschwörungsliteratur von den Anfängen bis zur Ur III-Zeit. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor philosophiae, Universität Jena 2111* (<http://www.db-thueringen.de/servlets/DerivateServlet/Derivate-32004/Diss/DoktorarbeitRudik.pdf>); A.R. George, *CUSAS* 32 (2016); A. Johandi, *The God Asar/Asalluḫi in the Early Mesopotamian Pantheon* (*Dissertationes Theologiae Universitatis Tartuensis* 37, 2019) passim.

Liebeszauber (3.8.2): Nouvelle traduction de ZA 56 (1964) 113-129 par W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/2* (1987) 208-210; M.J. Geller, *CRRAI* 47 (2002) 129 sq. et 135-139 (nouvelle édition).

Satiren (3.9): Pour Ugubi, cf. aussi Th. Jacobsen, *OIP* 98 (1990) 105 sq. et n. 25 et *ETCSL* 3.3.07 (2005).

Elegie auf den Tod des Nannamu (3.10.a) und Elegie auf den Tod des Nawirtum (3.10.b): *ETCSL* 5.5.2 (1998-1999) et 5.5.3 (1998-2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 258-263 (3.10.a). — Cf. T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature* (PH. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 108-114; A.C. Cohen, *AMD* 7 (2005) 50 sq.; A. Löhnert, dans: C. Felli (ed.), *How to Cope with Death: Mourning and Funerary Practices in the Ancient Near East. Proceedings of the International Workshop, Firenze, 5th-6th December 2013* (2016) 49-66.

Die drei Freunde aus Adab (3.10.c): B.R. Foster, *ANES* 6 (1974) 70-72 (édition); B. Alster, *JCS* 43-45 (1991-1993) 27-38 (édition); *ETCSL* 5.6.5 (1999); Alster, *Wisdom* (2005) 373-383 (édition). — Cf. A. Cavigneaux, *ASJ* 9 (1987) 51 sq.; W.G. Lambert, *NABU* 1995/2; Alster, dans: K. Eksell/L. Feldt (ed.), *Readings in Eastern Mediterranean Literatures* (2006) 72-75; Gadotti, *Sumerian wisdom literature* 65 sq., 67 sq., 71-73; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 61 sq.

"Home of the Fish" (3.10.d): *ETCSL* 5.9.1 (1999); Black et alii, *LAS* 240-244; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 104-111. — Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *OLA* 13 (1982) 311-319; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT* 307 (2003) 162 sq.; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* 488-495; A. Gadotti/A. Kleinerman, *NABU* 2017/39.

Liebeslieder (3.10.e): 27 compositions considérées comme des "love songs"³ ont été éditées en dernier lieu par Y. Sefati, *Love Songs in Sumerian Literature* [...], *Ramat-Gan*

³ Comp. aussi Å.W. Sjöberg, *JCS* 29 (1977) 16-27 et 39-43 n° 5; *CT* 58 12-14, 15 // 16 et 22; B. Alster, *ASJ* 14 (1992) 1-46.

1998; cf. également Alster, RA 79 (1985) 127-159 et Mél. Hallo 15-27 (riche bibliographie pp. 26 sq.; ajouter J.G. Westenholz, CRRAI 38 [1991, ed. 1992] 381-387); ETCSL 4.08./... (1998-1999). — J.S. Cooper, CM 7 (1997) 85-97; V. Haas, *Babylonischer Liebesgarten* [...], München 1999; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* passim; S. Tinney, JNES 59 (2000) 23-30; M.M. Fritz, AOAT 307 (2003) 69-96; P. Lapinkivi, SAAS 15 (2004) 30-50 passim; P. Mander, *Canti sumerici d'amore e morte* (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005); A. Zgoll, ZA 96 (2006) 109-119; Fritz, dans: B. Heininger (ed.), *An den Schwellen des Lebens. Zur Geschlechterdifferenz in Ritualen des Übergangs* (2008) 27-87; J. Klein/Y. Sefati, Mél. Paul (2008) 613-626; F.A.M. Wiggermann, RIA 12 (2009-2011) 411 sq.; Y. Sefati/J. Klein, *Two Dumuzi-Inanna Love Songs: Dumuzi-Inanna Q and an Unidentified Song*, Mél. Skaist (2012) 309-334; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 297-309; N. Wasserman, LAOS 4 (2016) (chants d'amour akkadiens); L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar* (2017) 31-59 passim; N.H. da Silva Ferreira, AOAT 460 (2020) 399-413.

Liebeslied Šulgis (3.10.e 1): ETCSL 2.4.2.26 (2000).

Liebeslied Šū-Sins (3.10.e 2): Nouvelles éditions: Alster, RA 79 138-142; Sefati, *Love Songs* 344-352; Th. Jacobsen, Mél. Pope 57-60; ETCSL 2.4.4.1 (1999). — Nouvelles traductions: Castellino, TSA 191-193; Kramer/Bottéro, *Mariage sacré* 112-114; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 95 sq.; P. Mander, *Canti sumerici d'amore e morte* (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005) 144-146; Attinger, TTS (2010, actualisé en 2017) (B); C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 105-110 (A et B). — Cf. Jacobsen, JCS 7 (1953) 46 sq. (= TIT 184-186); E. Sollberger, JCS 30 (1978) 99 sq.; D.R. Frayne, *BiOr.* 42 (1985) 9 sq.; M. Widell, JNES 70 (2011) 289-302.

Die Botschaft des Ludingira an seine Mutter (3.10.f): S.N. Kramer, *BiMes.* 4 (1976) 19-21; T.R. Kämmerer, AOAT 251 (1998) 13 sq. et 164-169; ETCSL 5.5.1 (2000); Black et alii, LAS 190-192; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 253-258; D. Arnaud, *AuOr-S* 23 (2007) 179-185 n° 50 (version d'Ugarit); A. Gadotti, Mél. Owen (2010) 115-129 (édition). — Cf. W. Heimpel, *StPohl* 2 (1968) 60-64; J.S. Cooper, *JBL* 90 (1971) 157-162; J. van Dijk dans J.P. Asmussen/*alii* (ed.), *Handbuch der Religionsgeschichte I* (Göttingen, 1971) 493 sq.; Wilcke, *UT* 151 sq.; M. Stol, *Women in Ancient Near East* (2016) 157; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 256-265; A. Cavigneaux, RA 114 (2020) 89.

Lugal-anne-mundu (3.10.g): Cf. D.O. Edzard, RIA 7, 1/2 (1987) 114 s.v. *Lugal-anne-mundu* (bibl.); Yang Zhi, *JAC* 4 (1989) 55-60.

Nanše und die Vögel (3.10.h): ETCSL 4.4.3 (2000); N. Veldhuis, CM 22 (2004) 115-142 (édition).

Ninurta und die Schildkröte (3.10.i): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 418-424; ETCSL 1.6.3 (1998); B. Alster, CM 35 (2006) 13-36 (édition); L. Feldt, dans: K. Eksell/L. Feldt (ed.), *Readings in Eastern Mediterranean Literatures* (2006) 83-127 (éd.). — Cf. Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 84-86; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 61 sq.; Wagensonner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 97-99; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* 456-467 (Il. 36-46); J.-D. Forest, *Mém. Bottéro* (2009) 47-53 passim.

Ochsenpflügerlied (3.10.j): ETCSL 5.5.5 (1999). — Cf. A. Livingstone, ZA 70 (1980) 55-57.

Ur-Nammus Tod (3.10.k): C. Wilcke, Urnammu's Tod [...] (ms. non publié); S.N. Kramer, Mél. Takahito Mikasa 193-214 (édition); E. Flückiger-Hawker, OBO 166 (1999) 93-182 (édition); ETCSL 2.4.1.1 (1999-2000); G. Pettinato, Mitologia sumerica (2001) 477-491; Black et alii, LAS 56-62. — Cf. T. Kuwabara, The Netherworld in Sumer-Akkadian Literature (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 114-119; G. Pettinato, I Sumeri (1991) 288 sq.; Rollinger, Frühformen 60-63; D. Katz, The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources (2003) passim, surtout 329-336 (index des lignes discutées p. 480); B. Studevent-Hickman, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), The Ancient Near East (2006) 61-65; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.), The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600 (2011) 17 sq.; Jordanova, A., Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015) 370-374; P. Steinkeller, CRRAI 60 (2017) 15 sq. avec n. 55; M.T. Sharlach, SANER 18 (2017) 176 sq.; C. Halton/S. Svärd, Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors (2018) 110-115 (ll. 1-216); E.S. Gerstenberger, Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen (= ORA 28, 2018) 111 sq.; A. Garcia-Ventura, CHANE 116 (2020) 226-228.

Wiegenlied (3.10.l): ETCSL 2.4.2.14 (2000); Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 265-270; K. Volk, dans K. Volk (ed.), Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer (2015) 83-88 et 418 sq.; C. Halton/S. Svärd, Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors (2018) 102-105. — Cf. B. Alster, RA 65 (1971) 170 sq.

